

Spoke 4

CITY, ARCHITECTURE,
AND SUSTAINABLE
DESIGN

**Leader: Università Iuav
di Venezia**

Research Topic

RT2.4

Living, usability, accessibility

DS4_RT2.4.1

Report on design for all
solutions to increase the
accessibility of public places
and facilities

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the activities conducted during **Milestone 4 (M29-M40)** within the RT2.4 activity “Living, Usability, Accessibility” of the iNEST Spoke 4.

The research activities, jointly coordinated and carried out by Università Iuav di Venezia and Università degli Studi di Padova, were conducted starting from the research programme main objective: optimising the usability and accessibility of urban areas, by considering the need to reduce barriers to improve the ease of navigation for both people with physical disabilities and the ageing population. The activities were therefore aimed at defining solutions to be implemented starting from the Italian North-East territory features, within the “design for all” approach, and especially by considering innovative and digital technologies as enablers in this process.

The research team brought together cross-cutting expertise from the fields of architectural technology, environmental psychology, and Human-Computer Interaction, which played a key role in defining and conducting the investigation by examining both physical and digital solutions and tools. By identifying the research scope, aim, and specific objectives, the investigation was structured in two parallel trajectories focusing on different topics: apps supporting inclusive mobility in urban spaces (i) and protocols and guidelines for inclusive urban spaces (ii). The activities were then divided into five different research actions:

- Comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps (i). A list of existing apps falling into the research scope was determined, and the related mapped services and interface features were examined. On this basis, the apps were comparatively assessed in order to identify and classify accessibility-related features.
- Comprehensive analysis of design-relevant aspects of mobile apps for inclusive urban mobility (i). Through a comprehensive analysis of relevant sources, design recommendations for inclusive mobile applications supporting urban mobility were identified, and areas for improvement were defined by comparing the findings with the examined apps.
- User-centred evaluation of accessibility features in urban mobility apps (i). The attitudes of different users towards the accessibility-related features offered by urban mobility applications were explored, and evidence on the perceived accessibility and usefulness of selected functions was collected to inform the design of more inclusive digital solutions and support inclusive planning strategies.
- Review of current tools, documents and protocols (ii). Existing frameworks pertaining to European and National standards, tools to assess neighbourhood sustainability, and other international documents were examined, and 127 design criteria improving quality of life in urban areas were recognised as relevant.
- Critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements (ii). 55 analysed criteria addressing physical elements in the built environment to increase the usability and accessibility of urban spaces were selected. Recurring themes and topics were identified, clustered, and classified into 15 specifications regarding physical features for improving the usability and accessibility of urban space for people with mild impairments and older adults.

The two research trajectories were conducted autonomously by different research teams, each guided by its disciplinary know-how and expertise, with constant confrontation and discussion of the intermediate results throughout Milestone 4. The methodological approach adopted in each action also varied depending on these circumstances and the specific objectives of the investigation:

- The comparative assessment of existing mobile apps was based on an initial screening of approximately 100 applications retrieved from major app stores. This process led to the selection of 24 apps addressing urban mobility, which were comparatively analysed (**Annex**

DS4_RT2.4.1-A1). Among them, five apps usable in the North-East Italian context and targeting motor impairments were further examined through an expert evaluation focused on accessibility-related features and information presentation.

- The identification of design-relevant aspects of mobile apps for inclusive urban mobility was based on recent literature retrieved from several research databases using pertinent keywords.
- The user evaluation involved people with motor impairments and caregivers, who assessed selected accessibility-related features of urban mobility apps in relation to everyday pedestrian mobility needs. Data on perceived usefulness, accessibility and improvement needs of these features were collected to support the development of more inclusive digital tools.
- The review of current tools, documents and protocols was performed by recognising and categorising the thematic areas and design elements aiming at improving quality of life based on the expressed objectives.
- The critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements was based on the clustering and categorisation of recurring elements through inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Overall, the research activities provided the following main results:

- The definition of a set of improvements in the features of existing navigation apps to support a more inclusive urban navigation.
- Design specifications at the neighbourhood scale to improve accessibility and usability of urban spaces for individuals with mild impairments and older adults were defined and further developed into the “Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces” guidelines (**Annex DS4_RT2.4.1-A2**).

Figure 01, at the end of the executive summary, summarises the structure of the research activity.

The deliverable is structured as follows. **Chapter 2** details the research scope and its outputs, starting from the role of RT2.4 within the iNEST research, the state-of-the-art it built upon, and the specific results in relation to its goal. It then outlines the methods adopted by the two investigation trajectories for each of the actions that were undertaken, the results achieved, and introduces the outputs' structure and contents. **Chapter 3** illustrates the correlation with the research projects funded by the cascade calls. **Chapter 4** provides the main references. **Annexes DS4_RT2.4.1-A1** and **DS4_RT2.4.1-A2** shall be considered as an integral part of the research.

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Figure 01. Overall structure of the iNEST Spoke 4 research “Living, Usability, Accessibility”.

2. RESEARCH AND OUTPUTS

2.1. ROLE OF THE RESEARCH ACTIVITY IN THE CONTEXT OF iNEST

Opposite to others, the RT2.4 activity “Living, Usability, Accessibility” operated with a significant extent of autonomy within the overall iNEST project, although the two main disciplines involved in the investigation are, of course, tied to other research activities - both previous and simultaneous (Milestone 4) ones. The main reason for this premise is the fact that RT2.4 is the sole one specifically devoted to fostering the usability and accessibility of public spaces and routes in urban areas.

The specificity of the investigation derives from the approach highlighted in the research programme, aimed at defining solutions and patterns for overcoming conflicts of liveability within the urban fabric by reducing architectural barriers and reducing the degree of exclusion that vulnerable people currently face. A peculiar aspect of this approach is its twofold perspective on the topic, dealing at the same time with the physical elements composing public spaces - squares, walkways, ramps, steps, crossings, etc., and digital ones - devices and technologies which could significantly improve the effectiveness of design for all solutions. The latter, examined and/or developed in RT2.4, were expected to target specific groups of individuals: elderly and people with disabilities (reduced mobility, visual impairments or mild cognitive impairments). These premises depict an operating context placing the research activity mainly within the social side of sustainability, as it addresses the needs of individuals to ensure quality of life for all. To guarantee the effectiveness of the process and identified solutions, a user-centred approach is fundamental and grounded in established knowledge from Human-Computer Interaction and environmental psychology, which provided the main conceptual framework for the investigation. On the other hand, the environmental design expertise played a key role as well, since the actions suggested or undertaken to eliminate existing obstacles and barriers inevitably interact with the urban fabric in its physical features as it currently is.

Included in RT2, the “Living, Usability, Accessibility” activity represents one of the five research actions with direct application to the territory of the Italian North-East, addressing the limits and criticalities of the latter to support its sustainable transition and increasing its resilience. Nevertheless, RT2.4 can also be considered a “node” between the innovative and technological solutions for the built environment (RT2) and the activities dedicated to understanding how the latter shape us as individuals and communities (RT3). In this sense, its results are linked to the iNEST trajectories investigating the relationship between individuals and their environment (RT3.1), including the ability of the latter to mediate human behaviour and emotions (RT3.2) and to improve the well-being and quality of life of fragile people (RT3.4). Nevertheless, the technical framework it was developed into, its operating context and specific scope - improving the ease of navigation in urban areas through an inclusive approach - impacted on the specialised nature of its results.

The topics addressed in this research activity also reveal a tight connection with one project funded within the second cascade calls framework, namely “Inclusive Domotic Environment for the Aged people” (IDEA). In fact, although focusing on interiors, the project aims to improve liveability and usability for elderly sharing the RT2.4 perspective on digital technologies and devices as enablers that improve the effectiveness of the solutions. Members involved in the research activity were therefore entrusted to provide technical-scientific support and to verify that the activities carried out by the beneficiary complied with the proposed work plan. The 12-months monitoring, which started in Milestone 3, also involved other cascade calls projects - as they were linked to the environmental design field and the sustainable improvement of the built environment. All these projects concluded their activity in November 2025.

2.2. DEFINITION OF THE RESEARCH PERIMETER

The research activity 2.4 did not stem from a previous investigation within the iNEST context; therefore, a more precise definition of the context and scope outlined in the research programme was necessary. In particular, as the general aim was summarised as improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces for vulnerable people by inclusive and innovative solutions, the way these terms were operationalised within the investigation needed to be clarified:

- Within the scope of the investigation, “vulnerable people” were operationalised as elderly individuals and persons with mild physical and/or sensory impairments, including individuals with mild cognitive impairments.
- “Innovative solutions”, were operationalised as “digital tools and physical solutions allowing an inclusive fruition of urban space”, excluding personal mobility aids for ambulation (e.g. wheelchairs, walkers) and indoor solutions, as these constitute individual assistive devices or interior-scale interventions rather than features of the urban environment, while inclusive means of designing and/or managing physical systems and infrastructure fell within it.
- Concerning “urban spaces”, the “neighbourhood scale” was adopted as a benchmark - with a focus on routes, services and points of interest (POIs). Setting this reference point impacted on the solutions to be identified, analysed, and tested. Moreover, given that each urban area presents different features, this approach allows the investigation to be scaled by applying the same process in other neighbourhoods, while, at the same time, leaving room for the methods’ flexibility.

Hence, the general aim of the “Living, Usability, Accessibility” activity was more precisely set as “identifying digital tools and physical solutions to improve usability and accessibility of urban spaces at the neighbourhood scale for the elderly and individuals with mild physical impairments”.

The emerging twofold perspective on solutions and tools led to the research being structured and conducted by two parallel trajectories. The first one focused on digital tools improving the inclusive fruition of urban space (i) and the second on the physical characteristics of the latter (ii). Both trajectories considered, by different perspectives, the solutions’ contents - meant as information conveyed (a), and usability - ease of access and understanding (b), according to the following articulation:

- i. The investigation addressed existing digital tools within the research scope, examining the types of content and services they provide (a) and their functional and inclusive characteristics (b).
- ii. The investigation was based on the relevant physical features of urban spaces enabling liveability and the means they adopt to improve access and usability of spaces. Hence, attention was paid to the specific features (“information”) of urban spaces (a) and the communication of this relevant information to stakeholders acting on their design and management (b).

The emerging background structure of the research led to defining the tools to be identified, examined and evaluated according to both the digital and physical perspectives adopted in the process. More specifically, the investigation targeted:

1. Apps supporting inclusive mobility in urban spaces.
2. Protocols and guidelines for inclusive urban spaces.

This twofold perspective enabled approaching the same overarching aim by different sides, in line with the different know-hows and disciplinary perspectives of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and environmental psychology, on the one hand, and architectural technology, on the other hand. By gradually interrelating the intermediate results of the trajectories, mutual insights and benefits were achieved.

2.3. GOAL AND SPECIFIC RESULTS

As described in [paragraph 2.2](#), the goal of RT2.4 research activities was set as identifying digital tools and physical solutions to improve usability and accessibility of urban spaces at the neighbourhood scale for elderly and individuals with mild physical impairments, considering, on the digital side, apps supporting inclusive mobility in urban spaces and, on the physical side, protocols and guidelines for inclusive urban spaces. The investigation was structured according to different actions and phases that were led in parallel within the two trajectories.

Comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps.

Two specific objectives were identified: (i) understand the current scenario concerning the existing apps supporting inclusive navigation in urban environments with details of their services and contents, and (ii) identify which accessibility-related features are currently implemented and how they are distributed across different applications.

This led to two outputs: (i) a structured framework detailing the features of 24 existing apps ([DS4_RT2.4.1-A1](#)), and (ii) the identification of a subset of 5 applications suitable for the subsequent user evaluation, based on the presence of features relevant for pedestrian accessibility for people with motor impairments.

Comprehensive analysis of design-relevant aspects of mobility apps for inclusive urban mobility

The specific objective was to identify potential areas for improvement in existing mobile apps that enhance the usability and accessibility of urban spaces for people with physical disabilities. This allowed integrating the set of issues and limits emerging from the comparative assessment into a set of cross-cutting design considerations.

User-Centred evaluation of accessibility features in urban mobility apps

The specific objective was to explore how users with motor impairments perceive and evaluate specific accessibility-related features implemented in urban mobility applications, in relation to their everyday pedestrian mobility needs. The output of this activity was a set of user-based findings describing the strengths, limitations, and improvement needs of these features in supporting pedestrian mobility.

Review of current tools, documents and protocols

The specific objective was scoping existing tools, documents and protocols supporting an inclusive urban navigation to identify suggested criteria for improving quality of life in outdoor environments at the neighbourhood scale. The result of this activity was a framework identifying and categorising thematic areas and indicators recognised as relevant in light of the actions' objective.

Critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements

Based on the previous review, the specific objective was to draw specifications for the design and management of public spaces by identifying, among the collected criteria, the ones addressing physical elements in the built environment, increasing the usability and accessibility of urban spaces. This included both the specific physical barriers to be avoided, as well as room for improvement to be seized. This action resulted in a framework categorising specifications explicitly addressing elements to implement in neighbourhoods, further developed into the "Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces" design guidelines ([DS4_RT2.4.1-A2](#)).

2.4. RESEARCH METHODS

Comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps

To define the current state of apps that support inclusive navigation in urban environments, it was necessary to build a comprehensive inventory of relevant mobility apps, including details on their features, content, and functionality.

Two different app stores were considered to ensure the largest possible share of mobile operating systems (OS) was covered by the investigation (Kumar, 2025): Google Play Store¹, providing software for the Android OS market, and the Apple App Store², providing applications for iOS devices (i.e., iPhones and iPads).

Consistent with the research scope and specific objectives, the two stores were searched using a predefined set of keywords. Specifically, a three-step search strategy was adopted:

- i. First, general terms related to disability and inclusion (e.g., “inclusive mobility”, “disability”, “people with disabilities”) were used to identify applications addressing accessibility.
- ii. Second, these terms were combined with mobility-related keywords (e.g., “travel”, “navigation”) to restrict the search to applications supporting urban movement and pedestrian navigation.
- iii. Third, additional searches were conducted using impairment-specific terms (e.g., “visual impairment”) to include applications explicitly developed for particular user groups that were not retrieved through the previous queries.

The search strategy yielded a pool of more than 100 applications. Applications were subsequently screened by store category to retain only those relevant to inclusive urban pedestrian navigation. Applications belonging to non-relevant categories (e.g., tourism-oriented services and vehicle-based apps) were excluded from the analysis.

This screening process resulted in the identification of 24 applications within the research perimeter. Each of the 24 applications was tested directly on the operating system(s) for which it was available (Android and/or iOS) in order to document its functional characteristics and to account for platform-specific differences where applicable.

All retrieved data were progressively organised into a structured table. Information was collected according to the parameters reported in Table 01, covering two categories:

- General information;
- Inclusivity-related information: target user group, services available to users (concerning navigation and POIs), and means of interaction with the user (both input and output).

General information

App name	Name of the application
Store	Store from which it can be downloaded or purchased
Store category	Maps and navigation, navigation, travel, local information, motor assistance
Issue date	Date of first release
Last update	Date of the latest update
App version	Number of the version
Free version	Existence of a free version, including most of the main features
Mobile/Web	Mobile app and/or web app
Contributive/Consultative	Contributive (crowd-based): users can add or update content, generating crowd-based accessibility information. Consultative: users can only search and view information provided by the system.

¹ <https://play.google.com/store>

² <https://www.apple.com/it/app-store/>

Geographical coverage	Area of the world covered by the app
Use of maps	Digital maps provided by external mapping services (e.g., Google Maps, OpenStreetMap, Mapbox)
Overall ratings	Average rating (1-5 stars) calculated from the total number of user ratings
Downloads	Total number of downloads of the app
Inclusivity-related information	
Services provided	Online navigation; route accessibility; route preview; points of interest (POIs); POI accessibility; user reporting (user-generated integration of map information); Augmented Reality (AR)/Virtual Reality (VR) features
Targeted end users	End users' type and degree of impairment (e.g., motor, visual, mild cognitive impairments)
APP Native Interaction Modality: INPUT	Audio, camera, text, touch
APP Native Interaction Modality: OUTPUT	Audio, tactile, video
Issues	Not working, Unavailable, No Italian version, Discontinued service, Georestricted – not available in Padova, Georestricted – not available in Venezia(*)

Table 01. Parameters considered to collect information on existing mobile apps supporting the navigation of older adults and individuals with mild physical impairments in urban areas.

Following the documentation of the 24 applications, a subset of applications was selected by applying predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Eligible applications were required to provide at least one service related to pedestrian navigation or accessible points of interest and to include users with motor impairments among their intended target groups. In addition, applications had to be operational within the geographical context of the study (North-East Italy, with a focus on Padua). Applications were excluded if they were not functioning, unavailable, discontinued, lacked an Italian version, or were not available in the study area (North-East Italy, with a focus on the urban areas of Padua and Venice). Table 02 illustrates the inclusion and exclusion criteria adopted for the selection of applications for expert evaluation.

Inclusion criteria

Provided service	At least one of the following services should be provided: - Selection of accessible POI - Selection of an accessible path - Navigation
Targeted end user	At least individuals with motor impairments should be included in the targeted end users

Exclusion criteria

Technical and availability status	Not working, Unavailable, No Italian version, Discontinued service, Georestricted – not available in Padova, Georestricted – not available in Venezia(*)
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(*) To perform the context-based evaluation, the app should be working in the iNEST Ecosystem territory, the Italian North-East, especially in the urban area identified for the evaluation, Padua (see also [DS4_IRM4](#) - "Summary of the activities of Milestone 4, January 2025 – June 2025").

Table 02. Inclusion and exclusion criteria applied for the expert evaluation.

The expert evaluation aimed to systematically analyse in depth the accessibility-related features implemented in the selected applications.

The analysis focused on two functional domains defined a priori as relevant for pedestrian accessibility: (i) accessibility-related information on points of interest (POIs), and (ii) support for pedestrian route accessibility.

Within each domain, accessibility-related features were identified through an exploratory analysis of the selected applications. An initial open screening was conducted to observe the types of accessibility-related information and functions provided by the apps. Based on this exploratory phase, recurring feature categories were defined and organised into two analytical grids, one for POIs and one for pedestrian routes.

These analytical grids were then systematically applied to all selected applications within the expert evaluation process. Each application was tested directly on the operating system(s) for which it was available. When an application was available on both Android and iOS, it was tested on both devices to account for potential platform-specific differences.

For each feature, evaluators independently recorded its presence and implementation characteristics. Discrepancies between evaluators were discussed until a consensus was reached.

Comprehensive analysis of design-relevant aspects of mobility apps for inclusive urban mobility

This activity was carried out through a comprehensive critical analysis of recent literature concerning current apps on inclusive mobility and social participation in urban spaces.

The analysis focused on studies that describe or evaluate mobile applications for urban mobility that address users with motor impairments or reduced mobility, as these provide concrete examples of how inclusive mobility needs are addressed in implemented systems. Conceptual or theoretical contributions not associated with a specific application were therefore not considered in this step of the analysis. Sources were considered if published between 2015 and 2025, written in English, and peer-reviewed. Literature was retrieved by four different databases (i.e., Scopus, Web of Science (WoS), PubMed, PsycInfo) through a field-based search targeting: (i) title of the paper, (ii) abstract of the paper. And (iii) keywords defined by the authors. The keywords used considered four different fields:

- Scope (e.g., "mobility", "navigation", "pedestrian", "environmental accessibility")
- Target (e.g., "motor impair*", "wheelchair user*")
- Tech (e.g., "app", "mobile app*", "web app*")
- Context (e.g. "urban environment*", "smart cit*", "urban space*")

The references considered are summarised in Table 03. They were analysed to identify explicit design recommendations for inclusive mobile applications supporting urban mobility, particularly those grounded in software validation. Only a limited number of studies reported guidelines derived from field-based evaluations or practical assessments of the proposed technologies; when available, these were mainly drawn from prior literature and used to inform the refinement of the application concept.

The same analysis also aimed to identify emerging critical issues, research gaps, and areas for improvement, as well as features, content, or insights concerning applications that stood out relative to others and the established state of the art. This information was considered as implicit suggestions that should be taken into account when designing inclusive mobile applications supporting urban mobility. The performed critical analysis addressed the following topics:

- Relevant technical aspects of the technologies described or assessed (e.g. web or mobile app, Operating System (OS), connectivity and positioning, possible integration with ATs, use of AR/VR features);
- End users targeted (possible specifications concerning the physical impairment, e.g., use of a wheelchair, extension to other groups of individuals besides disability, etc.).
- Functions included in the app (route computing, obstacles or barriers, POIs, modality for input and output, personalisation or customisation).
- Feedback concerning user experience (in case the paper reports a study)

- Emerging criticalities, research gaps, areas of improvement, particular features, contents or insights.
- Explicit guidelines.

Author(s)	Year	Developed app(s) or system(s)	Assessed app(s)
Achillas et al.	2023	Seek & Go app	-
Agarwal	2018	EasenAccess	EasenAccess
Araújo et al.	2024	BarrierBeGone	BarrierBeGone
Ajimi et al.	2019	"AR system for the assistance of wheelchair people" (concept)	-
Arellano et al.	2019	"Mobile Application Based on Dijkstra's Algorithm"	"Mobile Application Based on Dijkstra's Algorithm"
Comai et al.	2015	MEP project app	Comunepertutti, Mapability
Comai et al.	2017	MEP project app	-
Darcy et al.	2016	VilTech	VilTech
Darvishy et al. (*)	2022	Uncover	Uncover
Da Silva Lima et al.	2019	App for crowdmapping-based accessible - routes generation	-
Fatecha et al.	2021	SmartMoving mobile application	SmartMoving mobile application
Harriehausen-Mühlbauer B.	2016	WheelScout app	-
Harriehausen-Mühlbauer B.	2017	WheelScout app	-
Paiva et al.	2021	Viana + Acessível	-
Pankau (**)	2019	AXSMap Project, Talking Map (no development, description only)	-
Prandi et al.	2018	OpenTripPlanner (customised version)	OpenTripPlanner (customised version)
Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo	2017	GAWA (construction, generating and management of accessible Wayfinding Service) system	Assisted Multimodal Wayfinding Application (AMWA)
Shimokihara et al.	2021	-	Google Maps navigation app
Silva et al.	2023	Viana+Acessível	-
Shreepriya et al.	2018	We Care app	-
Vlahovic and Glazar	2018	"Urban accessibility app" (concept)	"Urban accessibility app" (concept)
Vaittinen and McGookin (*)	2018	Uncover	Uncover
Vargas-Acosta et al.	2019	Urban Connector	Urban Connector
Verde et al.	2021	Viana+Acessível mobile application	Viana+Acessível mobile application
Vincent et al.	2022	-	HERE WeGo pedestrian navigation app

(*) excluded as it does not address accessibility issues

(**) excluded as a theoretical contribution, only describing technological advancement contributions to spatial justice

Table 03. Literature concerning current apps and technologies on inclusive mobility and social participation in urban spaces. A distinction is made between contributions that describe only the structure and functioning of a developed application, project, and/or system, and those that also assess it through surveys, field tests, and/or user feedback.

User-centred evaluation of accessibility features in urban mobility apps

The study targeted individuals with motor impairments and caregivers or support persons who assist them in urban mobility, as pedestrian accessibility barriers directly affect their interaction with the built environment and the organisation of everyday mobility; for this reason, accessibility-related app features are particularly relevant for both groups. A protocol was developed to conduct a feature-based user evaluation of accessibility-related features available

across different urban mobility applications, selected through the preliminary expert evaluation (i.e., Kimap, WeGlad, Wheelmap, OsmAnd, Google Maps).

Accessibility-related features and evaluation scenarios. The evaluation focused on functions related to pedestrian accessibility, with particular attention on two main groups of features: (a) features supporting the assessment and selection of accessible Points of Interest (POIs), and (b) features supporting the identification and interpretation of accessible pedestrian routes.

Accessibility-related features were presented through screenshots prepared by the researchers, extracted from the selected applications and organised to highlight the specific characteristics of each feature and to show different examples of its implementation. This approach allowed participants to engage with the features in a simulated usage context, responding to the visual material “as if” they were interacting directly with the applications. During the sessions, participants were encouraged to verbalize their impressions, ideas, uncertainties, and potential difficulties, enabling the collection of spontaneous reflections and exploratory feedback on the accessibility-related functionalities.

The first group of features concerned the accessibility of POIs, including: overall accessibility, multi-component accessibility, qualitative user feedback, photographic accessibility documentation, filter by type, and filter by accessibility (Table 04).

Accessibility of Point of Interests (POIs)

Feature	Description	Application
Overall accessibility	Synthetic categorical rating of POI accessibility (e.g., accessible / partially accessible/inaccessible), typically shown directly on the map (e.g., colour-coded). Information is mainly user-generated through community contributions.	Kimap, Wheelmap
Multi-component accessibility	Accessibility information is provided for specific POI components (e.g., entrances, interior spaces, toilets) based on platform-defined attributes combined with user input.	Google Maps, OSMAND, WeGlad, Wheelmap
Qualitative user feedback	User-generated textual reviews describing accessibility conditions and contextual aspects of the POI (e.g., barriers, ease of movement, practical tips).	Google Maps, OSMAND, Kimap, WeGlad, Wheelmap
Photographic accessibility documentation	User-uploaded photographs documenting accessibility conditions of the POI and critical elements (e.g., entrance, interior spaces, toilets).	Google Maps, OSMAND, Kimap, WeGlad, Wheelmap
Filter by type	Filtering POIs by category (e.g., services, leisure), based on platform-defined POI classification systems.	Google Maps, OSMAND, Kimap, Wheelmap
Filter by accessibility	Filtering POIs based on accessibility criteria (e.g., only accessible or partially accessible POIs), derived from user-contributed accessibility data.	Kimap, Wheelmap

Table 04. Accessibility-related features for POIs are considered in the study and corresponding applications.

The applications reported in Table 04 correspond to those used to generate the screenshots shown during the evaluation and are intended as representative examples of systems implementing the analysed features, rather than as an exhaustive list of all applications offering such functionalities (Figure 02).

Figure 02. Examples of screenshots used to present accessibility-related features for POIs extracted from different applications.

The second group of features concerned pedestrian route accessibility. These included: accessible route tracing, information on road and surface type, slope, obstacle reporting, and street-level previews from both roadway and sidewalk perspectives (Table 05).

Accessibility of the pedestrian routes

Feature	Description	Application
Accessible route tracing	Computation and visualisation of a pedestrian route optimised for accessibility constraints (e.g., wheelchair-friendly). Route generation is provided by the application system.	Google Maps, OsmAnd
Road and surface type	Information on street typology and surface material (e.g., paved, unpaved, cobblestones), derived from map database attributes.	OsmAnd
Slope	Indication of route inclination and steep segments, computed from map and elevation data.	Google Maps, OsmAnd
User-reported obstacle	User-reported barriers such as roadworks, uneven terrain, and steep ramps, optionally accompanied by photographs.	WeGlad
Street view – roadway perspective	Panoramic preview of the route from the roadway perspective, provided directly by the official application provider (e.g., via integrated Street View imagery).	Google Maps
Street view – sidewalk perspective	Panoramic preview of the route from the sidewalk perspective, provided through integration with external street-level imagery services (i.e., Mapillary).	OsmAnd

Table 05. Accessibility-related features for pedestrian routes are considered in the study and corresponding applications.

To contextualise the evaluation of features, participants were introduced to short scenarios. For POI-related features, two scenarios were adopted:

- (i) an exploratory scenario, in which participants imagined planning an outing in the city with friends or family members and selecting places that would be accessible for everyone;
- (ii) an emergency scenario, in which participants imagined needing to quickly identify a suitable cashpoint to withdraw money at a local market.

For route-related features, an exploratory scenario was adopted. Specifically, participants imagined organising an outing in the city and selecting the most appropriate pedestrian route to reach a destination with others, identifying routes accessible to all and avoiding those affected by barriers.

Ethical aspects and recruitment. The study protocol was approved by the local Ethics Committee. Participants were recruited through an initial screening procedure based on the dissemination of infographics and invitation emails to public and private organisations, associations, and individual contacts. Interested individuals were subsequently contacted by telephone, during which the study aims, procedures, and participation conditions were explained in detail. The sample included individuals with motor impairments who were able to move autonomously as pedestrians and were familiar with smartphone use, as well as caregivers or support persons who regularly assist them in urban mobility and have direct experience in organising or supporting pedestrian mobility in the city. All participants received written information about the study and provided signed informed consent before participation.

Setting and equipment. The evaluation was conducted either in person at the University of Padua's research facilities or remotely, according to participants' preferences expressed during recruitment. In-person sessions took place in accessible spaces suitable for participants' mobility needs, while remote sessions were conducted via Zoom³ with screen sharing. Sessions were supported by a shared digital workspace (Miro⁴), which displayed screenshots of the evaluated features and organised interactions between researchers and participants. Two researchers were present in each session: one facilitated the interaction with the participant, while the second took structured notes and annotated participants' comments directly in the shared workspace (Figure 03). All sessions were audio- and video-recorded to enable accurate transcription and subsequent qualitative analysis and were supported by an interactive digital whiteboard and the Qualtrics⁵ platform for questionnaire administration. For in-person sessions, the research team provided a tablet for questionnaire completion; for remote sessions, the questionnaire was accessible via a direct link or a QR code, as participants preferred.

³ <https://zoom.us>

⁴ <https://miro.com>

⁵ <https://www.qualtrics.com/it/>

Figure 03. Example of an in-person evaluation session and shared digital workspace (Miro) used for feature presentation and annotation.

Measures. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, integrating quantitative and qualitative measures. This approach combined structured questionnaires with qualitative elicitation techniques to capture both measurable perceptions of accessibility-related features and in-depth insights into participants' reasoning.

Quantitative measures

- (a) Pre-session questionnaire: an online pre-experience questionnaire was used to characterise participants' mobility profiles, technology and app mobility use, and attitudes toward urban mobility apps. The questionnaire was administered in two parallel versions: one for individuals with motor impairments and one for caregivers or support persons, with items tailored to reflect whether participants experienced mobility limitations themselves or supported another person's mobility. The questionnaire included six sections:
- Socio-demographic and role-related information (8 items): age, gender, education level, occupation, city of residence, type of mobility-related disability (self or person assisted), mobility aids used by the person assisted, and level of autonomy in urban mobility.
 - Urban mobility habits and experiences (7 items): frequency of movement in the city, independent or accompanied mobility, and access to familiar and unfamiliar urban areas, with additional items adapted from Üstün et al. (2010).
 - Technology use and familiarity (8 items): frequency of smartphone use and familiarity with navigation and mobility applications (e.g., Google Maps, Apple Maps, Kimap, WeGlad, Wheelmap, OsmAnd).
 - Perceptions and acceptance of mobility applications (5 items), based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM; Davis, 1989).
 - Environmental barriers to mobility (2 items), (adapted from Vasudevan et al., 2015).
 - Travel-related anxiety (2 items). Two ad hoc items were developed to capture perceived anxiety associated with unexpected environmental barriers and inaccessible routes during urban mobility, drawing on disability research on participation restrictions and environmental constraints (Üstün et al., 2010).
 - A final open-ended section allowed participants to provide additional comments on their urban mobility experience.

- (b) Feature evaluation questionnaire: for each feature presented, a brief questionnaire was administered to assess participants' perceptions of the accessibility-related information provided by the feature. The questionnaire included four items measuring:
- Perceived usefulness, defined as the extent to which the feature was considered supportive of urban mobility decisions (Davis, 1989);
 - Perceived informational adequacy, referring to the extent to which the information provided by the feature was considered adequate to support mobility-related choices (Lee et al., 2002);
 - Perceived reliability, capturing the degree to which the information displayed by the feature was regarded as trustworthy (Wathen & Burkell, 2002);
 - Intention to use, defined as the likelihood of using the feature if available in one's mobility application (Spagnolli et al., 2014).

Responses were collected using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*).

Qualitative measures

Qualitative data were collected through open-ended questions and spontaneous participant comments during evaluation sessions to explore participants' reasoning and priorities regarding accessibility in urban mobility applications. This elicitation phase was grounded in established user-centred evaluation and verbalisation approaches. Three complementary types of qualitative inputs were collected:

- (c) Scenario-based questions. Open-ended questions were used to elicit participants' reasoning about accessibility in relation to the presented scenarios. These questions addressed factors influencing mobility experiences when users have to decide where to go, considering both POIs and route selection:
- characteristics that make a place or a route suitable for their mobility needs;
 - conditions leading them to exclude a destination or a path;
 - types of information considered necessary before deciding to move.
- (d) Feature-related qualitative feedback. After completing the quantitative questionnaire for each feature, participants were invited to comment on:
- positive aspects of the feature;
 - perceived limitations or problems;
 - suggestions for improvement.
- (e) At the end of each evaluation block (features related to POIs and features related to pedestrian routes), all previously presented features were summarised in the shared digital workspace (Miro). Participants were then asked a final open-ended question to identify which characteristics an "ideal" urban mobility application should include to best support accessibility needs related to POIs and to pedestrian routes, respectively, highlighting the most relevant aspects emerging from the evaluation.

Procedure. On the day dedicated to data collection, each session began with a brief introduction to the study, followed by the completion of the pre-session questionnaire.

POI-related features. Participants were introduced to an exploratory scenario in which they imagined planning an outing in the city with friends or family and selecting places that would be accessible to everyone. Contextual (scenario-based) questions were then asked to elicit participants' criteria and information needs related to the accessibility of places. The researcher subsequently presented the POI-related features using the prepared screenshots. For each feature, the following sequence was applied: presentation of the feature through screenshots (Figure 04), completion of the feature evaluation questionnaire, and collection of feature-related qualitative feedback. An emergency scenario was then introduced, in which participants imagined needing to quickly identify a suitable cashpoint to withdraw money at a local market. This scenario was used to evaluate POI filtering features (filter by type and filter by accessibility),

following the same sequence of feature presentation, questionnaire completion, and qualitative feedback. At the end of the POI evaluation block, all previously presented features were summarised in the shared workspace, and participants were asked to indicate which characteristics an ideal mobility application should have to best support accessibility related to points of interest.

Figure 04. Example of accessibility feature presentation during an in-person (on the left) and online (on the right) session.

Route-related features. Participants were subsequently introduced to an exploratory scenario in which they imagined organising an outing in the city and selecting the most appropriate pedestrian route to reach a destination with others, identifying routes accessible to all and avoiding those affected by barriers. Contextual (scenario-based) questions were again used to elicit participants' criteria and information needs related to route accessibility. The route-related features were then presented using screenshots. For each feature, the same sequence adopted for POI-related features was followed: presenting the feature through screenshots, completing the feature evaluation questionnaire (Figure 05), and collecting feature-related qualitative feedback.

Figure 05. Participant completing the Feature-Evaluation Questionnaire during the session.

At the end of the route evaluation session, all previously presented features were summarised in the shared workspace, and participants were asked to indicate which characteristics an ideal mobility application should have to best support accessibility related to pedestrian routes.

Finally, participants were thanked for their participation, and the session was concluded. The study procedure is summarised in Figure 06.

Figure 06. Schematic representation of the study procedure.

Review of current tools, documents and protocols supporting inclusive urban navigation

To achieve a structured and detailed list of documents that defined criteria for improving the quality of life and accessible navigation in outdoor environments, the investigation addressed literature. Existing documents were therefore screened, considering three main aspects:

- Their scope, meant as the expected context of application, concerning urban areas and neighbourhoods.
- They should pursue social sustainability, although the latter could have been just one of the three (or more) dimensions taken into consideration.
- They could be able to specify precise physical elements or design recommendations improving the quality of life in urban spaces through accessibility.

As no database could be used to run a proper search, the documents were selected by scoping online different top-down and bottom-up environments:

- European and national standards (namely, UNI EN and PEBA guidelines).
- International and national open access manuals included in different Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment (NSA) tools.
- Other relevant official guidelines and bottom-up documents deriving from previously examined tools.

All the sources were considered regardless of the specific stakeholder they addressed (es. Public Administrations, designers, end users). The following information was collected for each of the considered documents:

- Full title.
 - Year of publication and/or version.
 - Body or institution issuing the document.
 - Geographical area covered.
 - Topics or indicators concerning the inclusive nature of spaces at the neighbourhood scale - depending on the document's specific organisation and adopted glossary.
- Attention was paid to all entries inherent the elements or design approaches improving

quality of life, livability and accessibility in urban areas, regardless of the explicit reference to individuals with impairments or elderly. This approach was undertaken to achieve the most comprehensive list of inputs, to be later fine-tuned in the critical review process. All the information considered relevant was categorised by each document's thematic areas and design criteria, suggestions or specifications.

Critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements

To define specifications concerning precise physical elements of the built environment increasing the usability and accessibility of urban spaces, a critical analysis was carried out starting from the information retrieved by the review process. All entries previously identified (topics or indicators) were screened, to understand if they contributed by offering insights on specific physical barriers to be avoided as well as room for improvement to be seized for improving their usability and safe navigation in a design-for-all approach.

The analysis was carried out according inclusion and exclusion criteria:

- Criteria where no specific element to be designed or management was mentioned were excluded (e.g. the ones referring to general design approaches or objectives).
- Criteria addressing navigation of areas with specific functions (e.g. playgrounds, garden and parks) were included, but merged within the generic navigation specifications.
- Criteria only addressing characteristics, fruition, and usability of specific equipment (e.g. play equipment, ATMs, vending machines, type of vegetation species) not strictly inherent to navigation in urban areas were excluded.
- Criteria referring to the same element (e.g. route, seatings, pavement, parking facilities) were merged into a single specification.
- Off-topic criteria (not directly referring to inclusive features) were excluded.

This process allowed narrowing down the entries collected to a set of specifications directly addressing "physical features" to implement in outdoor urban areas for improving their usability and accessibility. The texts of the resulting specification were then analysed with the aim to identify recurrent elements or topics to which attention was given, to cluster them into a list of "Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces".

2.5. RESULTS

2.5.1. Digital tools improving the inclusive fruition of urban space

Comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps.

The comparative assessment of the 24 selected applications reveals a highly fragmented ecosystem of tools for inclusive urban navigation.

Most applications primarily address users with motor impairments (18 out of 24, 75%), while a smaller proportion explicitly supports users with visual impairments (6 out of 24, 25%), and only a marginal number targets users with mild cognitive impairments (2 out of 24, 8.3%). This distribution indicates a strong focus on physical accessibility, with more limited attention to sensory and cognitive needs.

Regarding core mobility functions, only 6 applications (25%) support selecting accessible points of interest (POIs), 5 applications (20.8%) support accessible path selection, and 6 applications (25%) include navigation functionality. Only 2 applications (8.3%) simultaneously integrate all three functions. These data show a marked prevalence of solutions oriented toward physical accessibility, with comparatively limited attention to sensory and cognitive dimensions.

Two applications (8.3%) include augmented reality features. Overall, 13 applications (54%) provide features that are available and usable within the North-East Italian context. However, most of these solutions focus primarily on the accessibility of POIs, while support for accessible route planning and navigation remains limited.

Applications addressing visual impairments mainly rely on audio-based descriptions of the surrounding environment, whereas those targeting motor impairments predominantly provide information on barrier-free routes adapted to specific mobility constraints.

Taken together, these results point to the absence of a single solution capable of comprehensively addressing different impairment types and mobility needs within a unified system. Figure 07 on the next page details the inclusivity-related information collected for the 24 identified applications. The full dataset considered for the comparative assessment (including both general and inclusivity-related information) is reported in Annex [DS4_RT2.4.1-A1](#). The structured comparative matrix of the 24 applications is presented in Table 06. It summarises their core accessibility services, target users, contextual availability, and technical issues, and provides the basis for the subsequent application of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

No. APP name	Services provided							End user targeted (impairment)			APP Native Interaction Modality INPUT				APP Native Interaction Modality OUTPUT		
	On-line Navigation	POIs	Accessible route	Accessible POI	Route preview	AR features	User report	Mild cognitive	Motor	Visual	Audio	Camera	Text	Touch	Audio	Tactile	Video
1 Maps AR	●	●			●	●		●				●	●	●	●	●	●
2 Kimap		●	●	●			●	●					●	●			●
3 Omniaroad				●			●		●				●	●			●
4 WeGlad				●			●		●				●	●			●
5 Wheelmap		●		●			●		●				●	●			●
6 Roll Mobility				●			●		●				●	●			●
7 OsmAnd	●	●	●	●			●		●				●	●	●		●
8 Mapillary					●				▲				●	●	●		●
9 Google Maps	●	●	●	●	●		●		●		●		●	●	●		●
10 Maps	●				●		●		●		●		●	●	●		●
11 Route4U	●	●	●	●			●		●				●	●			●
12 EasyWay Public Transport	●	●	●	●			●		●				●	●			●
13 Scotland transport Wheelchair	●	●	●	●			●		●				●	●			●
14 DeQua	●	●	●						●				●	●			●
15 WheeLog!	●	●		●			●	●	●				●	●			●
16 On wheels	Not understandable								●				●	●			●
17 Urbi	Position of shared vehicles only								●				●	●			●
18 WheelMate	Not working								●				●	●			●
19 Lazarillo	●	●					●			●	●		●	●	●		●
20 GoodMaps outdoor	●	●								●			●	●	●		●
21 Soundscape	●									●	●		●	●	●		●
22 NaviLens	Navigation through QR code										●		●	●	●	●	●
23 Moovit	●									●			●	●			●
24 Be my eyes	Remote assistance only										●	●	●	●	●		●

● Inclusivity-related feature present

▲ App not specifically designed for people with disabilities, but useful for those who need to know the condition of the road surface, sidewalks, steps, and pedestrian crossings.

Figure 07. Structured framework presenting the inclusivity-related information identified through the comparative assessment.

N.	Name	Suitable for the user assessment*		Selection of accessible POI		Selection of accessible path		Navigation		End users target (type of impairment)			Issues**
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Mild Cognitive	Motor	Visual	
1	Maps AR		•		•	•		•		•	•		C1
2	Keymap	•		•		•			•	•	•		C2
3	Omniaroad		•	•			•		•		•		C1 C2
4	WeGlad	• A		•		•			•		•		C3
5	Wheelmap	• A		•			•		•		•		C3
6	Roll Mobility		•		•		•		•		•		C7
7	OsmAnd	•		•		•		•			•		-
8	Mapillary		• B		•		•		•		•		C2 C5
9	Google Maps	•		•		•		•			•		-
10	Maps		•		•		•	•			•	•	C5
11	Route4U		•		• C		• D		• E		•		C1 C4
12	EasyWay Public Transport		•		• C		• D		• E		•		C1 C4
13	Scotland Transport: Wheelchair		•		• F		• F		• F		•		C1 C4
14	DeQua		•		• G		• G		• G		•		C1
15	WheeLog!		•		• H		• H		• H		•		C1 C3 C4
16	On wheels		•		• J		• J		• J		•		C1 C3
17	Urbi		•		• K		• K		• K		•		C6
18	WheelMate		•		• J		• J		• J		•		C7
19	Lazarillo		•		•		•	•				•	C8
20	GoodMaps Outdoor		•		•		•	•				•	C8
21	Soundscape		•		•		•	•				•	C8
22	NaviLens		•		•		•		•			•	C9
23	Moovit		•		• L		• L		• L			•	C6
24	Be My Eyes		•		• M		• M		• M			•	C2 C8

* **Area of implementation:** Padua/Veneto

** **Criteria:** C1 - Georestricted – not available in Padua; C2 - NO online navigation; C3 - NO online navigation (link to third-party apps); C4 - NO Italian version available; C5 - NO inclusive information related to POI; C6 - NO inclusive services; C7 - NOT working; C8 - NO motor impairment; C9 - NO mobility app

*** **Other specifications:** A - Only POIs survey; B - Only collaborative georeferenced mapping; C - Not possible in the Italian version; D - Selection of path only in few countries; E - Online navigation only in few countries; F - Only working in Scotland; G - Only working in Venice; H - Only working in Japan; J - Not working; K - Out of scope; L - No inclusive features; M - Remote assistance only.

Table 06. Results of the expert evaluation about comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps

While the previous analysis provides a general overview of the application landscape, a second-level analysis was conducted on a subset of five applications selected for in-depth assessment. This focused evaluation aimed to characterise in detail the accessibility-related features supporting points of interest (POIs) and pedestrian routes to inform the subsequent user-based evaluation phase.

With respect to points of interest (POIs), most applications provide multi-component accessibility information, while all include qualitative user feedback and photographic documentation. This indicates a common functional orientation toward documenting accessibility-related attributes at the POI level. However, filtering functionality varies substantially across applications: although Google Maps, OsmAnd, Kimap, and Wheelmap enable filtering by POI type, only Kimap and Wheelmap allow filtering by accessibility level.

Regarding route-related features, only Google Maps and OsmAnd provide accessible route tracking, and OsmAnd is the only application to offer additional attributes, such as road and surface type and sidewalk-level street view. Slope information is available exclusively in Google Maps, whereas user-reported obstacles are supported only by WeGlad. Street-level visualisation is unevenly implemented: both Google Maps and OsmAnd provide roadway perspectives, but sidewalk-specific views are available only in OsmAnd.

Overall, the results indicate that existing applications tend to prioritise accessibility information for POIs rather than comprehensive support for accessible route planning (Table 07). Each application addresses specific aspects of accessibility, but no single solution integrates all POI- and route-related features in a unified and consistent manner. This underscores the fragmented nature of current accessibility support for urban pedestrian mobility.

Comparative assessment of five selected applications: type of accessibility-related features

Feature	Google Maps	OsmAnd	Kimap	WeGlad	Wheelmap
Overall level of accessibility (POI)	-	-	•	-	•
Multi-component accessibility (POI)	•	•	-	•	•
Qualitative user feedback (POI)	•	•	•	•	•
Photographic accessibility documentation (POI)	•	•	•	•	•
Filter by type (POI)	•	•	•	-	•
Filter by accessibility (POI)	-	-	•	-	•
Accessible route tracking	•	•	-	-	-
Road and surface type	-	•	-	-	-
Route slope info	-	•	-	-	-
Obstacle reporting	-	-	-	•	-
Street view – roadway perspective	•	•	-	-	-
Street view – sidewalk perspective	-	•	-	-	-

• = feature offered by the app
- = feature not offered by the app

Table 07. Results of the tests on five selected apps, carried out on mobile devices.

Comprehensive analysis of design-relevant aspects of mobility apps for inclusive urban mobility

Although all the analysed applications share the overarching goal of facilitating inclusive urban navigation, they differ significantly in terms of target users, technological infrastructure, data acquisition methods, interaction modes, and personalisation strategies. The following section systematically examines these dimensions in order to identify design-relevant aspects for mobile applications supporting inclusive urban mobility.

End users are, in most cases, generally described as individuals with permanent or temporary physical disabilities or impairments (Agarwal, 2018; Arellano et al., 2019; Comai et al., 2015, 2017; Da Silva Lima et al., 2019; Fatecha et al., 2021; Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016; Prandi et al., 2018; Shreepriya et al., 2018; Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). Some applications, however, were specifically developed to support wheelchair users (Ajimi et al., 2019; Araújo et al., 2024), Wheeled Mobility Device (WMD) users (Vincent et al., 2022) or older adults (Shimokihara et al., 2021; Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). Other contributions adopt a broader understanding of urban accessibility, extending the scope to a wider target group sharing similar accessibility requirements: not only persons with disabilities or limited mobility, but also senior citizens, expectant mothers, and users with baby carriages (Achillas et al., 2023; Paiva et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2023; Verde et al., 2021). In two cases, a design-for-all approach was adopted: one application is conceived for all types of impairment (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017), and another for all individuals aiming to gain situational awareness of their immediate environment (Vaittinen and McGookin, 2018).

From a technical perspective, most applications are designed for smartphones, while fewer also provide a web interface (Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016; 2017; Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017) or adopt adaptive layouts for different screen sizes, including tablets (Ajimi et al., 2019; Da Silva Lima et al., 2019; Prandi et al., 2018). To enable users to input data (e.g., the presence of accessibility obstacles or a destination) and receive outputs contextualised within the urban fabric, the analysed solutions generally rely on georeferenced maps and GPS-based positioning to determine the user's location in real time (e.g., Araújo et al., 2024; Paiva et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2023; Verde et al., 2021; Vincent et al., 2022). Most of them collect data along the route using common hardware sensors such as GNSS, accelerometer, magnetometer, gyroscope, and barometer, which are embedded in the current generation of smartphones and tablets (e.g., Comai et al., 2017; Fatecha et al., 2021).

For outdoor navigation, several apps rely on Google Maps as a base mapping service (e.g., Achillas et al., 2023; Agarwal, 2018; Ajimi et al., 2019; Arellano, 2019; Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017; Shimokihara et al., 2021; Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019), while others use OpenStreetMap (Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016; Prandi et al., 2018). In addition to these base mapping infrastructures, several works further enrich the cartographic layer by integrating dedicated georeferenced datasets describing streets, obstacles, and urban barriers (Achillas et al., 2023; Agarwal, 2018; Araújo et al., 2024; Arellano et al., 2019; Paiva et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2023; Verde et al., 2021; Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018) in some cases, this accessibility modeling extends to building entrances (e.g., Achillas et al., 2023; Araújo et al., 2024). Others also allow indoor navigation based on fire escape plans of public buildings (Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016), or by exploiting the connectivity of Bluetooth beacons (Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016; 2017; Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017). In two cases, an AR navigation system is paired to an Android OS-based application, allowing users to connect smart glasses or smart bands (Ajimi et al., 2019; Prandi et al., 2018). Finally, one of the developed applications presents an architecture designed for synchronising local storage with the remote database, preventing data loss if the mobile connection is interrupted (Achillas et al., 2023).

While all the apps aim to improve accessibility of urban space, they contribute to this objective by different approaches. Achillas et al. (2023) do not incorporate routing calculation in the functions; however, the tool they developed enables data sharing to third-party systems, which can utilize the collected information to propose alternative access routes. Vargas-Acosta et al. (2019) provide the user with access to route generation using the third-party tool Google Maps, reducing the information needed to customise route preferences. The tool proposed by Harriehausen-Mühlbauer (2016) identifies barrier-free routes between two outdoor locations and, for indoor endpoints of public buildings, uses a traffic light metaphor to describe the accessibility level of the path. Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo (2017) offer a step-by-step multimodal guidance during navigation in outdoor environments. Vlahovic and Glazar (2018) developed an application relying on the same end users, individuals with physical impairments using the app, who trace barrier-free routes and can integrate accessibility obstacles and specific information about barriers in the map. According to this approach, as the number of routes gradually increases, the system assigns accessibility-based priorities during computation. Also, the app developed by Da Silva Lima et al. (2019) is based on crowdsourced inputs provided by the system users themselves (the obstacles mapped), suggesting routes that have low chances of having accessibility traps. In Fatecha et al. (2021), routing is based on minimising traversal difficulty according to user-defined severity levels, and routes can be recalculated when accessibility reports are confirmed or resolved. In the Viana+Acessível framework (Paiva et al., 2021; Verde et al., 2021), routing is performed on pre-classified street segments defined in collaboration with local associations, using weighted shortest-path algorithms; this approach was later extended through a multi-objective optimisation model combining accessibility, slope, and time parameters (Silva et al., 2023). As Comai et al. (2017) point out, individuals with motor impairments can automatically map accessible itineraries as the application runs and records all the sensors' data. Arellano et al. (2019) allow users to define a path between a starting point and a destination, calculating the shortest itinerary through an algorithm that computes the lowest route value. Ajimi et al. (2019) added to this same feature a display of the travelling distance and expected duration of navigation time. In case of recently or real-time added obstacles, the application automatically updates the original calculation of the optimal route. Moreover, their work also conveys this information by a twofold output, both on AR glasses and by audio, allowing individuals in wheelchairs an easier interaction with their environment. Prandi et al. (2018) developed a smart glasses screen augmented with notifications and graphical elements to guide the user toward the destination, and a bracelet that vibrates to notify of turns and wrong directions.

The type of obstacles or POIs and related information also vary depending on the app. Araújo et al. (2024) identified six primary barrier types through user interviews, including physical obstacles, steep ramps, stairs, blocked access, parking misuse, and absence of ramps, with parking-related issues emerging as the most frequently reported. Reported barriers are subject to a three-vote validation mechanism, whereby reports receiving three negative votes are flagged as unreliable. Harriehausen-Mühlbauer (2016) addresses a series of mobility barriers, each of which can be easily identified at the interface thanks to self-explanatory icons: all items can be supplied with information on the accessibility level and marked as permanent or temporary (automatically removed after 2 days). Da Silva Lima et al. (2019) permit users to photograph a location that presents accessibility traps for low-mobility people, to mark a map marker on that site, to rate it by its level of difficulty, to classify it by the type and to upload the picture taken. Comai et al. (2017) also suggest a pre-defined set of obstacles among which to choose by touch, adding information on its permanence and the criticality level (low, medium, high). Some pictures and a description can be included, if desired. In Fatecha et al. (2021), reports of accessibility problems or accessible amenities (e.g., lack of accessible crossings, degraded/non-existent sidewalk, stairs, vehicle obstruction, or ramps and accessible bus stops)

are described and associated with a structured status workflow (unknown, confirmed, resolved) supported by user confirmations and resolution actions.

Agarwal (2018) identified 12 parameters describing the following items to be identified in urban areas (that should be pre-mapped and assessed by expert evaluators): Dedicated Parking, Route, Ramps, Hand Rails, Steps, Entrance, Internal Doors, Corridors, Surface, Lift, Toilet, and Internal Stairs. Arellano et al. (2019) only focus on the presence of ramps, while Ajimi et al. (2019) address building accessibility levels, with symbols to alert to the obstacles' presence in real time. Vargas-Acosta et al. (2019) allow the elderly to locate the nearest available parking lots, find out how many parking spots are still available, and be reminded of where they parked and how much time remains on their parking time. Information about relevant transportation services can also be accessed. Vlahovic and Glazar (2018) propose connecting to a dedicated, pre-structured GIS database containing all relevant information on accessibility, the public transportation system, public service locations, and building layouts. A rating system details each barrier offering the application users also the chance to upload the related pictures.

Most of the developed apps rely on user contributions for content and data generation. Many allow the users to add obstacles to the map (e.g., Ajimi et al., 2019; Araújo et al., 2024; Fatecha et al., 2021), including a short description (Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016) or a rating on the degree of accessibility (Comai et al., 2017; Da Silva Lima et al., 2019). Participation, however, takes different forms across the examined systems. Achillas et al. (2023) structured a survey to be filled out to correctly insert the new item in the map as a graphical element. Users are provided with clear guidance on selecting the appropriate entity from a range of options, including street segments, POIs, segment connections, and POI/entrance. A similar institutional and expert-driven data contribution model, rather than direct crowdsourcing, is adopted in the Viana+Acessível system, where accessibility data and street classification are provided and validated by the City Council and representative institutions (Paiva et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2023; Verde et al., 2021). In some cases, thanks to the users' input, the system is able to recognise main travel incentives and preferred routes, recommending the best ones to individuals with similar preferences (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). In fact, by crowdsourcing means, users' added obstacles can trigger the navigation suggestions when looking for the most suited route (Da Silva Lima, 2019; Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). Comai et al. (2017) identify a path taken mostly by people with disabilities as a friendlier route; this allows their application to automatically identify accessible paths without the need for an ad-hoc field survey, simply because the traveller who captures the data has been registered to have some specific impairment. Similarly, in participatory routing systems, user-generated accessibility reports may influence subsequent route computation once confirmed or updated (Fatecha et al., 2021).

The analysis reveals how the tools mainly adopt touch for the input and visual map-based interfaces for the output as modes of interaction with the user (Achillas et al., 2023; Agarwal, 2018; Araújo et al., 2024; Comai et al., 2017; Da Silva Lima et al., 2019; Fatecha et al., 2021; Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019; Verde et al., 2021; Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018), although some works also adopted more means such as speech recognition or voice output (Agarwal, 2018; Ajimi et al., 2019; Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016; Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017; Shimokihara et al., 2021; Vincent et al., 2022). One case even tested the use of smartphone vibration and sign language on screen (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017).

Personalisation is considered an important feature, as impairments vary significantly from one individual to another. Many of the examined applications can be customized so that the routes are individually computed on the basis of a personal profile or selected user segment, which is matched against the features of the barriers; users can save frequently used POIs or itineraries (Ajimi et al., 2019; Fatecha et al., 2021; Harriehausen-Mühlbauer, 2016, 2017; Paiva et al., 2021; Prandi et al., 2018; Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017; Silva et al., 2023; Verde et al.,

2021; Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). One research developed the app so that users with a sensorial, cognitive or physical disability are all able to access it, as people without a disability: the application only changes the interface features (colors, buttons and dimensions) and content (text, cognitive maps, multimedia, audio or subtitles) (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017). Gamification engagement mechanisms are introduced in some cases, through individual user profiles, scoring systems, rewards, and leaderboards to foster user engagement and recognition (e.g., Araújo et al., 2024).

Recommendations and suggestions

Explicit recommendations are proposed by Vargas-Acosta and colleagues (2019). They outline sixteen recommendations for smart mobility applications for seniors: (R1) applications should be intuitive, simple and easy to use; (R2) avoid overly invasive data requests impacting privacy; (R3) be inexpensive or free of charge; (R4) provide large fonts for visual impairments; (R5) provide speech-to-text and text-to-speech; (R6) provide directions based on real-time traffic; (R7) core functionality should be available offline; (R8) provide ADA-compliant alternate transportation modes; (R9) use updated maps of ADA-compliant sidewalks and ramps; (R10) help find parking stalls; (R11) ask user consent for anonymous data sharing; (R12) allow preferred interface language; (R13) provide access to relevant resources and events; (R14) recommend restaurants according to dietary needs; (R15) allow reaching emergency contacts; (R16) implement gamification to incentivize use.

Some examined research carried out field tests to assess the developed prototype or tool and received feedback (Achillas et al., 2023; Ajimi et al., 2019; Araújo et al., 2024; Comai et al., 2015, 2017; Fatecha et al., 2021; Prandi et al., 2018; Shimokihara et al., 2021; Shreepriya et al., 2018; Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019; Vincent et al., 2022; Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). Across the studies reporting user evaluations—typically conducted through field tests, controlled route tasks, questionnaires, or semi-structured interviews—four recurrent dimensions emerge as central to user experience refinement: interface, contents, mode(s) of interaction and personalisation. Although the participants in the studies were the prospective end-users themselves, and therefore their feedback should be contextualised to the specific circumstances (e.g., focus on wheelchair users only, evaluation conducted within predefined mobility scenarios), several recurring patterns can be identified across studies, suggesting cross-cutting design considerations:

- Regarding the interface, the graphics' dimensions and readability were among the topics that several participants in the studies raised. The use of simple and readable icons (Comai et al., 2015), and no more than a few of them per menu would allow clarity, as well as a limited number of steps (“taps”) to access a service, which would ease access to the application (Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). Adjustable text and graphic size also emerged as relevant. In this respect, task-based usability testing in BarrierBeGone led to interface-related recommendations, including increasing text size for readability and allowing users to bypass or revisit onboarding steps via their profile (Araújo et al., 2024). The size of visualised elements also becomes an issue when interacting with the device through touch; in fact, users with restricted hand movements may have difficulty selecting lines and icons (Comai et al., 2015). The design phase should focus on improving the tolerance of tap precision on the screen, as well as facilitating the actions required to the user (e.g., facilitating drag&drop processes on the map through sticky elements) or implementing the serialization of actions (e.g. use of consequent taps on elements; Achillas et al., 2023). Similarly, SmartMoving evaluations showed that some key buttons on the main screen were confusing (e.g., users selecting a ramp-related control instead of the intended “add report” action), suggesting that primary CTAs should be clearly

distinguishable and that report actions can be grouped in a single, explicit control area (Fatecha et al., 2021). The amount of information provided on the barriers should also avoid a high number of details on the screen, a circumstance making it difficult to get immediate information (Comai et al., 2015) - using pictures could be more intuitive as well as focusing the app development on larger screen devices through a tablet-first design (Achillas et al., 2023). In addition, map markers based only on severity colours were not always sufficient: while users interpreted the traffic-light metaphor, they did not always understand which incident type each marker referred to, highlighting the need to combine colours with explicit incident icons on the map (Fatecha et al., 2021). Similarly, participants using wheeled mobility devices identified ease of access and hands-free use among the most important usability criteria, indicating that interface design should support quick access and stable interaction without requiring continuous manual handling of the device (Vincent et al., 2022).

- On the side of contents, not only the possibility for users to add items on the map appears fundamental, but also features allowing specifying their type and degree (Ajimi et al., 2019) or adding information about them (Comai et al., 2015). Data on accessibility barriers or obstacles should be provided by filling simple and brief evaluation forms, and could benefit from the update of pictures giving a better idea of their relevance depending on each individual specific impairment (Comai et al., 2017). It is preferable for an application to suggest accessible routes rather than one only signalling obstacles (Comai et al., 2017), and real-time display of the resulting time and distance when modifying the itinerary to an alternative one is appreciated. (Ajimi et al., 2019). Recommendation of routes based on prior travel generators is considered reliable if it refers to itineraries already validated by similar user profiles (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). Nevertheless, a critical side of participatory tools is that users should actively and frequently update the applications in order to make them sustainable and reliable (Comai et al., 2015). Besides paths and possible barriers, contents related to accessibility could address in detail several POIs such as buildings (Comai et al., 2015) (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018), public transportation stops (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018), parking lots (Comai et al., 2015), and provide information related to other services for disabled people (Comai et al., 2015). User evaluations further show that the perceived “severity” of the same barrier type varies substantially across individuals. In SmartMoving, a limited agreement emerged when categorising reports as mild or severe, indicating that severity levels should be configurable per user (or mobility profile) rather than fixed globally (Fatecha et al., 2021). Empirical navigation trials with WMD users also revealed frequent encounters with unannounced barriers (e.g., damaged or congested sidewalks, road works), and discrepancies between planned and actual travel time, suggesting the need to integrate more reliable and mobility-relevant information on sidewalk conditions and unexpected obstacles (Vincent et al., 2022). Consistently, requirements interviews conducted for BarrierBeGone identified six primary obstacle categories to be reported (barriers, steep ramps, large stairs, blocked access, improperly occupied parking lots, and absence of ramps), with parking misuse emerging as the most frequently mentioned issue (Araújo et al., 2024).
- With reference to the modes of interaction, users consider receiving information and feedback in real time very useful; moreover, when more than one mode of alert is introduced (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017) and in case they need to redirect their routes (Prandi et al., 2018). This is particularly relevant in the circumstances in which the environmental conditions would hinder the effectiveness of one application feedback only, e.g. by combining audio and vibration outputs (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017). Multimodality is appreciated also when audio is an input modality (Ajimi et al., 2019): speech-to-text supports users with typing impairments to enter information via voice instead of multiple clicks, and text-to-speech ensures that seniors

with low vision receive the same information included in texts using voice (Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). Combining several modes of interaction supports a design-for-all approach, including among the end users not only individuals with reduced mobility and using different aids (Comai et al., 2015), but also those with visual, hearing or typing impairments. This design feature avoids target groups being excluded. Consistently, older adults completed the route faster when guidance was combined on-screen and audio instructions (navigation app) compared to visual-only aids, suggesting a benefit of multi-sensory cues for route execution time (Shimokihara et al., 2021). However, real-world navigation trials also revealed criticalities in voice guidance: verbal indications were sometimes delivered too early, too late, or were absent; these timing issues affected efficiency and were perceived as potentially compromising safety (Vincent et al., 2022). These findings suggest that the effectiveness of multimodal interaction depends on adequate timing and reliability. In the SmartMoving study, users also suggested voice commands as an alternative way to create reports, in order to reduce reliance on touch interaction while moving (Fatecha et al., 2021).

- Also, personalisation of application features appears to be a shared concern in the feedback from participants assessing the different tools. In particular, the following aspects appear relevant: customisation of the routes, obstacles and POIs according to specific disabilities (e.g., manual vs. electric wheelchair) (Comai et al., 2015) (Comai et al., 2017). The user profile may include home address, frequently used locations, the preferred mode of transportation, preferred route type, emergency contacts, and medical conditions (Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). As described regarding the interface and modes of interaction, the selection of language, font size, and input/output modes should also be personalised. In addition, SmartMoving indicates that personalisation may also concern how obstacles are categorised and weighted (e.g., allowing users to classify negative reports as mild or severe according to their mobility needs) (Fatecha et al., 2021). Similarly, findings from WMD users underline the relevance of personalised accessibility parameters (e.g., slope, curb height, width) to better reflect individual mobility constraints during navigation (Vincent et al., 2022). In older adults, navigation performance in the app-based task was associated with mobile device proficiency and years of device use, suggesting that user profiles may differ substantially in digital skills relevant to navigation performance (Shimokihara et al., 2021). BarrierBeGone further couples participation with profile-linked engagement mechanisms (scoring, rewards, leaderboards) intended to motivate users to contribute barrier reports (Araújo et al., 2024).

A critical analysis of the examined contributions allows us to highlight three further aspects relevant in applications improving urban mobility, connectivity and quality of data, data acquisition, functions and ease of usage:

- Connection and quality of data. It should be important for the app to function even without internet access, allowing local data to remain in synchronization with the used database (Achillas et al., 2023), and irrespective of the continuity of GPS information (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017). These services could be offered by temporarily storing or caching data in the device (Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019) and monitoring content updates (Achillas et al., 2023). Nevertheless, this objective is hard to achieve when functions are expected to rely on real-time information (Vargas-Acosta et al., 2019). Connection status and features also affect the upload of information and pictures. In the first case, geo-positioning acquisitions of mobile devices could present a lot of noise, and it could be necessary to merge these data with a more precise device to provide a better estimation of the correct path (Comai et al., 2017). In the second case, links to the pictures should be available in various resolutions, given the challenge of

supporting high-quality images generated by current mobile cameras (Achillas et al., 2023). Another important feature to consider is the average battery consumption required by the app running, also in the background (Comai et al., 2017).

- Data acquisition. Participatory features, although prone to a lack of precision, represent a valuable means to acquire information. In particular, crowdmapping represents a means to value first-hand information that users themselves collected (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018; da Silva Lima et al., 2019). Collaborative systems also provide feedback on current access problems around the city and serve as support to monitoring and maintenance of these locations (da Silva Lima et al., 2019). In fact, this data can be validated and supplied to local authorities to prioritise incentives for urban accessibility improvements in line with the needs of their citizens. (Vlahovic and Glazar, 2018). Data included should provide information and guidance in normal situations, but also in emergency ones (for instance, accessible evacuation of a building) (Rodriguez-Sanchez and Martinez-Romo, 2017).
- Functions and ease of usage. Given the used device, touch and video represent the minimum input and output modes, respectively, and clear guidance on selecting icons, items to be added, and the route destination is necessary (Achillas et al., 2023). This requires tap-friendly UI interaction in relation to the screen size. SmartMoving evaluations indicate that easily overlooked instructions, complex interactions such as drag&drop, and prematurely visible action buttons may generate confusion; embedding contextual guidance and progressively disclosing actions can therefore enhance usability (Fatecha et al., 2021). In addition, during real travel WMD users often relied on device supports (e.g., straps or wheelchair fixation) and still encountered navigation obstacles, reinforcing the need to support hands-free use and minimise interaction demands while moving (Vincent et al., 2022). Similarly, in older adults' route tasks, the study notes that error reduction may be expected through learning how to use the navigation app, pointing to the relevance of familiarity and support in use (Shimokihara et al., 2021). In BarrierBeGone, task-based tests were overall completed with high execution ratings (average 4.57/5), but identifying barriers within a 50 m radius was more challenging, indicating a need to refine that function and/or related instructions; user feedback also pointed to improving onboarding accessibility (Araújo et al., 2024). Graphic visualisations could also be devised to display the collected information with different angles, e.g. highlighting critical areas for accessibility through heatmaps (Da Silva Lima et al., 2019). Safety could be considered, including a location-based SOS feature (Agarwal, 2018).

User-Centred Evaluation of Accessibility Features in Urban Mobility Apps

Sample. Information about the study was disseminated to over 30 organisations, associations, and local entities operating in the field of disability and mobility in the Padova area. Individuals who expressed interest were screened according to the inclusion criteria and subsequently enrolled in the study.

The final sample consisted of six participants, including three individuals with motor impairments and three support professionals (one educator, one occupational therapist, and one psychologist). Two of the support professionals also reported providing mobility support in their personal lives to individuals close to them. Among participants with motor impairments, different levels of severity were reported (mild to severe), primarily affecting lower limbs and overall motor functioning. Two participants reported regular use of both manual and electric wheelchairs, and one additionally reported the use of a walker. Among support professionals, the assisted persons generally presented moderate motor impairments, primarily affecting the lower limbs. The most frequently reported mobility aid was the wheelchair (manual or electric), in one case complemented by a powered add-on device.

Participants' mean age was 28.5 years (SD = 3.94; range = 25–36 years). The sample included four women and two men. All participants reported daily smartphone use. Responses to the technology-use section of the pre-session questionnaire indicated prior experience with at least one mainstream navigation application (e.g., Google Maps and Apple Maps). In contrast, familiarity with specialised accessibility-oriented applications (e.g., Kimap, WeGlad, Wheelmap, and OsmAnd) was limited and unevenly distributed across participants. Overall, self-reported technology use suggests that participants possessed adequate digital competence to meaningfully engage in the feature-based evaluation.

With respect to session modality, one session was conducted in person and five were conducted remotely via videoconference, according to participants' preferences.

Participants expressed a generally positive orientation toward mobility applications. Perceived usefulness in facilitating urban mobility and supporting autonomy was moderate to high (M = 3.50). Most notably, intention to use mobility applications in the future showed complete agreement across participants (M = 4.00; SD = 0.00), indicating a consistently positive disposition toward continued adoption. Regarding environmental constraints, participants reported occasional renunciation of mobility due to physical barriers (M = 2.50) and moderate concern about encountering inaccessible or dangerous obstacles during route planning (M = 3.67). These findings confirm that accessibility-related barriers remain a relevant factor in participants' urban mobility experiences.

Quantitative evaluation of accessibility-related features. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the limited sample size, quantitative responses were analysed descriptively. For each feature, means and standard deviations were calculated for perceived usefulness, perceived informational adequacy, perceived reliability, and intention to use. Results are presented separately for POI-related features (Table 08) and pedestrian route-related features (Table 09).

Among POI-related features, photographic accessibility documentation received the highest mean scores for perceived usefulness (M = 4.83, SD = 0.41) and intention to use (M = 4.83, SD = 0.41), and the highest score for perceived informational adequacy (M = 3.83, SD = 0.41). It also showed the highest perceived reliability (M = 4.33, SD = 1.21).

Multi-component accessibility and filter by accessibility were also evaluated positively across dimensions. Both obtained a mean score of 4.50 for perceived usefulness (SD = 0.55 and SD = 0.58, respectively). Intention to use reached 4.67 (SD = 0.52) for multi-component accessibility

and 4.75 (SD = 0.50) for filter by accessibility. For filter by accessibility, perceived informational adequacy and perceived reliability both yielded mean scores of 4.00 (SD = 0.00).

Overall accessibility showed a mean score of 4.00 (SD = 0.63) for perceived usefulness and 4.33 (SD = 0.52) for intention to use. Perceived informational adequacy was lower (M = 3.00, SD = 0.89), while perceived reliability reached 3.33 (SD = 0.52).

Qualitative user feedback displayed greater variability across dimensions, particularly for perceived usefulness (M = 3.50, SD = 1.64) and intention to use (M = 3.33, SD = 1.63). Perceived informational adequacy for this feature was 3.00 (SD = 0.89), and perceived reliability was 3.67 (SD = 0.82).

Filter by type received the lowest mean scores across all dimensions, with perceived usefulness at 2.80 (SD = 0.84), perceived informational adequacy at 2.40 (SD = 1.14), perceived reliability at 2.40 (SD = 0.89), and intention to use at 3.00 (SD = 1.00).

	Overall Accessibility	Multi-component accessibility	Qualitative Feedback	Photo Doc.	Filter Type	Filter Accessibility
Dimension	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
Perceived usefulness	4.00 (0.63)	4.50 (0.55)	3.50 (1.64)	4.83 (0.41)	2.80 (0.84)	4.50 (0.58)
Perceived info adequacy	3.00 (0.89)	3.50 (0.84)	3.00 (0.89)	3.83 (0.41)	2.40 (1.14)	4.00 (0.00)
Perceived info reliability	3.33 (0.52)	3.67 (0.52)	3.67 (0.82)	4.33 (1.21)	2.40 (0.89)	4.00 (0.00)
Intention to use	4.33 (0.52)	4.67 (0.52)	3.33 (1.63)	4.83 (0.41)	3.00 (1.00)	4.75 (0.50)

Table 08. Descriptive Statistics for the Evaluation of Accessibility-Related Features for Points of Interest (POIs).

Among route-related features, perceived usefulness ranged from 3.83 (SD = 0.98) for road and surface type to 4.67 for slope (SD = 0.52), user-reported obstacle (SD = 0.82), and street view – sidewalk perspective (SD = 0.84). Street view – roadway perspective showed a mean usefulness score of 4.33 (SD = 0.82).

Perceived informational adequacy was 3.50 for road and surface type (SD = 1.22), slope (SD = 0.84), user-reported obstacle (SD = 1.05), and street view – roadway perspective (SD = 1.05), while street view – sidewalk perspective reached a higher mean of 4.33 (SD = 1.03).

Perceived reliability ranged from 3.67 for road and surface type (SD = 0.52) and slope (SD = 0.52), to 4.17 for user-reported obstacle (SD = 0.75), 4.33 for street view – roadway perspective (SD = 0.82), and 4.50 for street view – sidewalk perspective (SD = 0.84).

Intention to use was highest for street view – sidewalk perspective (M = 5.00, SD = 0.00), followed by street view – roadway perspective (M = 4.83, SD = 0.41) and user-reported obstacle (M = 4.67, SD = 0.82). Road and surface type and slope information both showed mean intention-to-use scores of 4.17 (SD = 1.17 and SD = 0.75, respectively).

	Road & Surface Type	Slope Info	User-Reported Obstacle	Street View – Roadway	Street View – Sidewalk
Dimension	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)

Perceived usefulness	3.83 (0.98)	4.67 (0.52)	4.67 (0.82)	4.33 (=0.82)	4.67 (0.84)
Perceived info adequacy	3.50 (1.22)	3.50 (0.84)	3.50 (1.05)	3.50 (1.05)	4.33 (1.03)
Perceived info reliability	3.67 (0.52)	3.67 (0.52)	4.17 (0.75)	4.33 (0.82)	4.50 (0.84)
Intention to use	4.17 (1.17)	4.17 (0.75)	4.67 (0.82)	4.83 (0.41)	5.00 (0.00)

Table 09. Descriptive statistics for the evaluation of accessibility-related features for pedestrian routes.

User Perspectives on Urban Accessibility and Application-Integrated Accessibility Features.

Qualitative data were analysed using content analysis. Audio and video recordings were reviewed, and participants' comments were transcribed and organised according to the structure of the evaluation. Findings are presented in two parts: (1) criteria emerging from scenario-based discussions and (2) feedback related to the accessibility features presented during the evaluation.

Scenario-Based Criteria for Points of Interest (POIs). Across both exploratory and emergency scenarios, participants described accessibility as a multidimensional condition rather than a purely binary attribute. The suitability of a place was primarily associated with step-free access, the presence of ramps or lifts, adequate entrance width, and the availability of accessible toilets. Internal spatial layout was repeatedly mentioned, including manoeuvring space for wheelchairs, absence of narrow passages, and sufficient turning radius.

Beyond structural characteristics, predictability emerged as a relevant element. Participants emphasised the importance of anticipating spatial conditions in advance, particularly in unfamiliar environments. The accessibility of the surrounding urban space and proximity to other accessible services were also considered when evaluating a destination.

Conditions leading to exclusion included steps at the entrance, inaccessible or poorly maintained restrooms, steep or irregular ramps, uneven flooring, and cluttered interiors. In addition to physical barriers, incomplete or overly generic information was described as limiting autonomous decision-making. Uncertainty itself was perceived as a barrier, especially in emergency situations requiring rapid interpretation of accessibility indicators.

Participants also referred to contextual elements influencing perceived accessibility. In some cases, the presence of staff or other people was described as potentially mitigating minor barriers, as assistance could compensate for certain physical constraints. Conversely, crowded environments were mentioned as potentially limiting manoeuvrability and autonomy, even in structurally accessible spaces.

Regarding information required prior to deciding, participants indicated that synthetic accessibility labels were insufficient when presented alone. They expressed the need for detailed breakdowns of specific components (e.g., entrance, interior, toilets), contextual descriptions of real conditions, and visual documentation such as photographs. Additional information concerning surface conditions, door opening systems, and potential temporary obstacles was considered relevant for informed decision-making.

Scenario-Based Criteria for Pedestrian Routes

In discussing route selection, participants emphasised safety, continuity, and physical effort. Suitable routes were described as those ensuring uninterrupted step-free progression, smooth and stable surfaces, manageable slopes, and the absence of unexpected barriers. Dropped kerbs, protected crossings, and adequate sidewalk width were also identified as relevant elements.

Conditions leading to route exclusion included steep inclines, cobblestones or irregular pavements, narrow sidewalks, lack of curb ramps, and temporary obstacles such as roadworks or parked vehicles obstructing passage. Participants highlighted that even short inaccessible segments could compromise the usability of an otherwise suitable route.

As in the case of POIs, uncertainty regarding route conditions was considered problematic. Participants expressed the need to anticipate slope intensity, surface material, and potential interruptions before departure. Visual preview tools were described as useful for assessing spatial configuration and identifying potential critical points. Route-related information was framed as essential for both physical feasibility and for reducing anxiety associated with unexpected barriers.

POI-Related features

- Overall accessibility. Overall accessibility was perceived as useful for rapid orientation, particularly when displayed directly on the map and supporting an initial screening of POIs. Synthetic labels were considered practical in both exploratory and time-sensitive situations. At the same time, categorical classifications such as “accessible” and “partially accessible” were described as difficult to interpret in the absence of clearly stated criteria. Identical labels were reported to correspond to heterogeneous real conditions across locations, and the meaning of “partially accessible” was considered especially dependent on which specific environmental components were involved. Without explicit definitions, overall labels were perceived as informative but limited. Variability across individual mobility profiles and situational conditions was also mentioned. The relevance of certain elements—such as restroom accessibility—was described as context-dependent (e.g., short visits versus longer stays, independent versus accompanied mobility). In light of this variability, some participants indicated that overall classifications would be more supportive if complemented by clearer criteria, component-level detail, and greater flexibility in filtering accessibility according to personal and contextual parameters.
- Multi-Component accessibility. Multi-component accessibility was positively evaluated because it reflected participants’ own assessment logic. Distinguishing between entrance accessibility, interior circulation, and restroom accessibility was described as particularly meaningful, as the inaccessibility of a single component could compromise the usability of the entire POI. Compared to global labels, this feature was perceived as more informative and aligned with real decision-making processes. Some participants indicated that the usefulness of this feature would increase with clearer definitions of each component and more consistent representation across locations. In some cases, it was suggested that a more detailed specification of barriers or facilitators within each component would further support informed choice. In this perspective, participants also noted that the possibility of filtering these individual components directly in the map visualization would be highly desirable. Such functionality would allow users to tailor the information to their specific mobility needs and situational priorities, reducing cognitive load and avoiding the need to open each POI individually. Component-based filtering was therefore considered important for supporting faster and more reliable decision-making, especially in exploratory contexts or when planning routes under time constraints.
- Photographic documentation. Photographic documentation was frequently described as supportive in anticipating real spatial conditions. Visual evidence was perceived as more concrete than textual descriptions, especially in unfamiliar environments, as it allowed users to independently interpret ramp inclination, doorway width, or available manoeuvring space. Participants also suggested that the usefulness of photographic documentation could be further improved by introducing a system of visual references or framing guidelines (e.g., standard angles, reference

markers, or distance indications) to help contributors capture images in a more consistent and interpretable way, thereby increasing comparability and reliability across locations.

- **Qualitative user feedback.** Qualitative user feedback was valued for providing contextual detail and practical insights. Participants also noted that this feature becomes particularly meaningful for accessibility, as users with disabilities can often recognize comments provided by people with relevant direct experience—such as persons with disabilities or caregivers—which increases trust in the validity and practical usefulness of the information. A critical issue, however, is the lack of filtering mechanisms that allow users to easily identify reviews containing accessibility-related information.
- **Filtering Functions.** Accessibility-based filtering was considered supportive in reducing search effort, especially in emergency scenarios. However, a key limitation remains the lack of possibility to select the specific criteria that define the accessibility of a POI, preventing users from tailoring the results to their own functional limitations and situational needs.

Across POI-related features, participants recommended integrating synthetic indicators, component-level detail, and photographic documentation within a coherent interface. They suggested including update timestamps and clarifying the criteria underlying accessibility classifications. Greater personalisation options were proposed to allow users to select accessibility parameters aligned with their specific mobility profiles.

Route-Related Features

- **Accessible Route Tracing.** Route computation labelled as “accessible” was generally appreciated, as it reduced the need for manual inspection. However, participants indicated that the absence of transparency regarding the criteria applied in route calculation limited confidence in the suggested paths. Greater clarity about underlying parameters was suggested.
- **Slope and Surface Information.** Slope indication was described as particularly relevant, especially when related to physical effort and safety. Participants suggested that more precise representations, such as gradient percentages or segment-based details, would improve usability. Information on road and surface type was valued but sometimes perceived as too general to fully anticipate comfort or stability.
- **User-reported obstacle.** User-reported temporary barriers were considered useful for anticipating unexpected disruptions. At the same time, participants highlighted the importance of timely updates and mechanisms to ensure the temporal validity of such reports. In this perspective, a two-level model was hypothesized. The first level would be application-managed, based on integrations with external data sources—such as official information on the start and end dates of construction works and municipal open-data portals reporting road and sidewalk closures—so that the platform itself could automatically ingest, structure, and temporally regulate known disruptions. The second level would be participatory, allowing users to validate or question reported obstacles through lightweight interaction mechanisms (e.g., a “like” or confirmation function), enabling distributed verification and rapid validation of reported obstacles.
- **Street-Level Preview.** Street-level visualisation, particularly from the sidewalk perspective, was positively evaluated for enabling visual assessment of spatial configuration and potential critical points. Visual preview tools were described as supporting anticipation and reducing uncertainty before departure.

Participants proposed integrating route accessibility information, real-time obstacle reporting, slope and surface detail, and visual preview within a unified and customisable routing system. The possibility of personalising routing criteria according to individual mobility needs was repeatedly mentioned. Stronger integration between route planning and

POI accessibility information was described as a desirable characteristic of an ideal application.

Overall, qualitative findings provided interpretative depth to the quantitative trends observed in the feature evaluation. Features that obtained the highest mean scores—such as photographic documentation, multi-component accessibility, and sidewalk-level street view—were described as particularly effective in reducing uncertainty and enabling anticipatory decision-making. Conversely, features showing lower or more variable quantitative ratings—such as overall accessibility labels or generic filtering options—were qualitatively associated with ambiguity, lack of transparency, or insufficient personalisation. Taken together, the results indicate that accessibility-related digital tools are valued not only for the information they provide but also for their capacity to enhance predictability, trust, and perceived control over mobility decisions.

2.5.2. Physical features of urban spaces improving liveability, access and usability

Review of current tools, documents and protocols supporting inclusive urban navigation.

Based on the aspects described in **paragraph 2.4.1** (scope, contents specifying physical elements or design recommendations, pursuit of social sustainability), the 12 documents reported in Table 10 were identified:

No.	Full Title	Year/version	Geographical coverage	Body or institution
1	UNI EN CEI 172010 Accessibilità e usabilità dell'ambiente costruito – Requisiti funzionali*	2021	IT	UNI (Ente Italiano di Normazione)
2	Linee Guida interdisciplinari per la redazione del PEBA della Regione Emilia-Romagna	2024	IT	Regione Emilia-Romagna, CERPA
3	BREEAM Communities	2012/rev. 2017	UK	Building Research Establishment (BRE)
4	CASBEE-UD*	2014	JP	Japan Sustainable Building Consortium (JSBC) and Institute for Building, Environment and Energy Conservation (IBEC)
5	GBC Quartieri**	2015 (ITA)	IT	Green Building Council Italia (GBCI)
6	EcoDistrict	2018	US	EcoDistricts
7	Living Community Challenge	2019	US	International Living Future Institute
8	DGNB-Districts	2020	DE	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen (DGNB)
9	Just Communities	2023	US	Partnership for Southern Equity
10	One Planet Living	2025	UK	Bioregional and One Planet Living
11	Quality of Life Framework 2.0	2024	UK	The Quality of Life Foundation
12	My Neighbourhood	2024	World	United Nations - Habitat (UN-Habitat)

* In this case, the only analysed open-access document is the Technical manual.

** The document is the Italian version of LEED-Neighbourhood Development (2018, US). The text was translated from the Italian version and could differ from the US original text.

Table 10. Protocols and guidelines supporting inclusive urban navigation.

Among them, one is a National standard deriving from the related European one [1], one is a set of guidelines developed by a regional institution as a guidance relevant for the whole Italian territory [2], eight are NSA tools [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] [10], one is a framework developed by a non-profit association [11] and one provided by a global institution [12]. Due to this categorisation, the documents differ in the stakeholder addressed:

- The first type is a mandatory standard “describing the basic minimal functional requirements and recommendations for an accessible and usable built environment according to the "Design for All"/"Universal Design" approach, to allow an equitable and safe use for the most part of users, including people with disabilities” (UNI, 2021). Its contents must therefore be observed by all private or public actors intervening in the design phase.
- The second type supports Italian Public Administrations in drafting the Plans for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers (PEBA), introduced in the national legislation by Law 41/1986 and mandatory for all public bodies managing buildings and spaces open to the public (Regione Emilia-Romagna, CERPA, 2024). Although their implementation is not compulsory, the guidelines include information strictly pertaining to the investigation topic.

- The third type of documents includes tools conceived to quantify the environmental, social and economic impacts of residential, industrial or commercial neighbourhoods, in case of both new construction or redevelopments (BRE, 2017) (DGNB GmbH, 2020) (EcoDistricts, 2018. (GBCI, 2015) (Institute for Building Environment and Energy Conservation, 2014) (ILFI, 2017) (One Planet Living, 2019; 2025) (Partnership for Southern Equity, 2023). They are mostly used as a checklist to achieve a specific sustainability performance and are used by actors involved in the planning, design, delivery, regulation, and evaluation of urban developments at the neighbourhood scale. Depending on the objective, these actors can be Public Administrations, planners, designers, developers, consultants, researchers, policy-makers, or communities. These assessment tools become compulsory only if a PA decides to enforce them to ensure specific quality objectives in a specific construction or redevelopment.
- The fourth type of documents aims to improve the quality of life in urban spaces by prioritising health and well-being in the design of the built environment (Quality of Life Foundation, Community Fund, 2024) (UN-Habitat, 2024). They are voluntary, non-profit and open-access schemes. The first one supports local communities, professionals, and policymakers in planning, designing and managing urban spaces with a high quality for users, while the other is a toolkit promoting sustainability and resilience at the neighbourhood scale in the design process.

Following the identification of the 12 documents, their contents were screened to precisely characterise the criteria to which attention should be paid when designing urban spaces to improve quality of life by an inclusive approach. In this phase, all potential elements or approaches that could positively impact the liveability of outdoor environments were considered. Tables 11-22 in the following pages report all the information retrieved and organised per each document, divided into “Topic(s)” - i.e. the categories, areas of applications or fields each of the standards, protocols or guidelines identifies, and “Indicator(s)” - meaning the specific criteria, suggestion, tip (or indicator) presented for improving quality of life. Explicit target user groups of each reference are reported below the related tables. Overall, a total of 127 indicators were identified and categorised.

For conciseness purposes, not all the information provided per indicator/topic was reported, as it can be consulted in the reference itself. Particularly detailed information was included in the case of [8] as it is the only NSA tool thoroughly specifying design elements.

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s) **
Accessible and usable pedestrian areas. The main design considerations may include the separation of pedestrian and vehicular areas, effective wayfinding signage, step-free accessible routes, pedestrian crossings, acoustic and tactile guidance, adequate visual contrast and lighting, and the provision of resting areas at regular intervals.	1 Accessible pedestrian routes within pedestrian areas and at street crossings.
	2 Effective wayfinding signage (e.g. directional signage, clearly legible text and numbers).
	3 Separation of pedestrian, cycling, and vehicular areas (e.g. through curbs or tactile surfaces).
	4 Use of uniform, stable, and slip-resistant paving, ensuring adequate visual contrast.
	5 Step-free accessible routes (e.g. connecting ramps).
	6 Tactile ground surface guidance, particularly at intersections.
	7 Absence of obstacles or appropriate marking thereof, including adequate route widths.
	8 Acoustic guidance, particularly at pedestrian crossings.
	9 Adequate lighting, uniform along the route; artificial lighting should not cause direct or reflected glare.
	10 Provision of resting areas along pedestrian zones.
	11 Handrails for support and guidance on stepped routes, preferably on both sides.

	12	Protective guardrails along accessible routes at changes in level (with significant drops relative to ground level).
Accessible and usable equipment and facilities. Key design considerations may include intuitive operation, adequate maneuvering space and operating heights, multisensory information, and tactile controls.	13	Accessible routes to equipment (e.g. ATMs, ticket vending machines)
	14	Simplified and intuitive user interfaces, with readable text (including Braille), adequate visual contrast, and multisensory information (e.g. textual, acoustic, tactile).
	15	Appropriate operating heights (e.g. for children, wheelchair users, and very tall individuals) and adequate maneuvering space, including proper lighting.
Wayfinding. It describes a system through which appropriate information is provided to support individuals in navigating the built environment (buildings and outdoor spaces) toward a specific destination.	16	Placements that highlight essential elements such as entrances and services, preferably located at the beginning of the route.
	17	Adequate lighting.
	18	Clear and multisensory information.
	19	Adequate visual contrast.
	20	Provision of tactile guidance or tactile ground indicators.
	21	Routes coded through differentiated paving or color schemes, avoiding surfaces that may hinder orientation.
Urban furniture. Urban furniture may include street signs, waste bins, seating, bollards, streetlights, public transport stops, planters, hanging baskets for floral displays, and signs mounted on plinths, poles, or walls. Large spaces such as squares and plazas may also feature public art and water fountains.	22	Local public transport stops (bus, tram).
	23	Seating, in visual contrast with the surrounding environment and positioned in a space that does not obstruct circulation.
	24	Bollards, where necessary.
	25	Presence of flowers, vegetation, or moving water, which contributes not only to climate mitigation but also to wayfinding in open spaces.
Vegetation. Trees and plants enhance the pedestrian experience by serving as visual and auditory boundaries between pedestrians and traffic, but they can also obstruct pedestrian movement if not carefully positioned or pruned.	26	Placement outside the clear width of accessible routes, marked with guardrails or grids to be detectable with a cane.
	27	Attention to species selection (e.g., branches should not obstruct overhead clearance, fruits may pose hazards, pollen may affect individuals with allergies, etc.).
Bicycle Parking	28	Should accommodate bicycles and motorcycles of various sizes and provide adequate capacity.
	29	Should be easily identifiable and, if possible, covered.
Public toilet facilities	30	Restroom facilities should be clearly identifiable and appropriately signposted.
Playgrounds	31	Accessible routes and clear signage of entrances, particularly for individuals with visual impairments.
	32	Tactile orientation maps at the entrance to indicate the main facilities.
	33	Provision of inclusive elements and play equipment.
Gardens and parks	34	Pedestrian areas should be equipped with an effective drainage system to prevent water stagnation and accumulation.
	35	Surface materials should be selected with future maintenance needs in mind.
	36	Rest areas.
	37	Signage and information.
	38	Vegetation.
Public transports	39	Bus and tram stops, easily identifiable from a distance and through tactile or acoustic means; they should provide information on routes and destinations and offer shelter and seating with appropriate height, backrests, and armrests.

* Target user groups: all user groups, focusing on people with disabilities.

** The text was translated from the Italian version of the standard and could differ from the EN original text.

Table 11. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [1].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
-	- The document identifies the main areas of application of a PEBA, as well as the phases for its drafting, approval, and monitoring. Therefore, with respect to the objectives set by activity 2.4, it is not considered useful. Reference is made to the paragraph on inclusive urban safety (box "Urban Considerations") as the sole list of "improvement elements" to be taken into account.

* Target user groups: all user groups, focusing on people with disabilities

Table 12. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [2].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Social and economic wellbeing	1 06_Delivery of services, facilities and amenities Provision of facilities and their walking distance
	2 07_Public realm To encourage social interaction by creating comfortable and vibrant spaces in the public realm
	3 08_Microclimate To ensure the development provides a comfortable outdoor environment through the control of climatic conditions on a micro scale
	4 10_Adapting to climate change To ensure the development is resilient to the known and predicted impacts of climate change
	5 11_Green infrastructure To ensure access to high-quality space in the natural environment or urban green infrastructure for all
	6 15_Inclusive design To create an inclusive community by enhancing accessibility for as many current and future residents as possible
	7 16_Light pollution To ensure that the lighting on site is designed to reduce light pollution
Transport and Mobility	8 02_Safe and appealing streets To create safe and appealing spaces that encourage human interaction and a positive sense of place
	9 03_Cycling network To promote cycling as a leisure activity and as an alternative to vehicle use by providing a safe and efficient cycle network
	10 04_Access to public transport To ensure the availability of frequent and convenient public transport links to fixed public transport nodes (train, bus, tram or tube) and local centres
	11 05_Cycling facilities To promote cycling by ensuring the adequate provision of cyclist facilities
	12 06_Public transport facilities To encourage frequent use of public transport throughout the year by providing safe and comfortable transport facilities

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 13. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [3].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Environment - Nature	1 <u>Greenery</u> In particular, ground greening (calculation of greening ratio)
	2 <u>Corridor (network) quality</u> Evaluation of a network with peripheral natural space through a corridor or the like
Society - Impartiality/Fairness	3 <u>Area management</u> Existence of a neighbourhood association or organisation to involve the inhabitants in the block
	4 <u>Traffic safety</u> Establishing sidewalks for securing pedestrian safety and existence of plans of movement lines
	5 <u>Crime prevention</u> The level of efforts for security measures, including night lighting, monitorable characteristics from the periphery, and security cameras in the block
Society - Amenity	6 <u>Convenience/welfare</u> Standard distance or time distance for some facilities
	7 <u>Culture</u> Creation of culture, view (landscape).
Economy - Traffic/Urban structure	8 <u>Traffic</u> Facilities in the district (level of roads, parking lots, bicycle parking, ..)
	9 <u>Usability of public transportation</u> Distance of the bus stop in combination with a measure for a comprehensive transportation system.
Society - Social Services (from CASBEE City manual)	10 <u>Adequacy of cultural services</u> (availability of community centers and libraries)
	11 <u>Adequacy of medical services</u>
	12 <u>Adequacy of childcare services</u>
	13 <u>Adequacy of services for seniors</u>

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 14. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [4].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s) **
Neighbourhood organisation and planning	1 <u>Pedestrian usability of streets</u> Promote transport efficiency, including the reduction of kilometers traveled by private car. Encourage walking by providing safe, attractive, and comfortable urban routes, with the aim of promoting public health, reducing pedestrian-involved accidents, and supporting daily physical activity. This concept is linked to mixité (shops and street-facing storefronts).
	2 <u>Visitability and universal accessibility</u> Enable broad groups of citizens, regardless of age or ability, to participate more easily in community life, thereby increasing the usable areas for people with diverse abilities.
	3 <u>Tree-lined avenues and shaded streets</u> Encourage walking, cycling, and public transport use, while discouraging excessive vehicle speed. Reduce the urban heat island effect, improve air quality, increase evapotranspiration, and lower building cooling loads. >> Provide shading through the placement of trees or other structures along at least 40% of the block length on sidewalks within the project's internal street network.

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

** The text was translated from the Italian version of the protocol and could differ from the English version.

Table 15. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [5].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Equity (imperative indicator)	1 <u>Physical surroundings</u> 1. Walkability score 2. Number of civic centers/healthy food stores within walkable distance 3. Amount of green spaces within walkable distance
Place (priority indicator) Create inclusive and vibrant communities	2 <u>Public spaces</u> 1. Public spaces are accessible to all 2. Public spaces are high-quality, engaging and active
Health and wellbeing (priority indicator) Nurture people's health and happiness	3 <u>Active living</u> 1. Access to recreation facilities and services is improved 2. Walkability is enhanced
	4 <u>Safety</u> The built environment is designed for public safety
Connectivity Build effective connections between people and places	5 <u>Street</u> 1. The street network supports all travel modes 2. The street network accommodates people with diverse ages and abilities
Living Infrastructure Enable and connect to flourishing ecosystems	6 <u>Natural features</u> Natural features are protected
	7 <u>Connection with nature</u> Access to nature is improved

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 16. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [6].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Places Creation of good places to live, considering that human behavior and attitudes are the most significant barriers to transforming our developed surroundings.	1 <u>Imperative 04_Human-powered living</u> Creation of walkable, pedestrian-oriented communities and cyclable. >> A walkway network comprised of enhanced pedestrian routes.
Health and Happiness to create robust, healthy Communities filled with happy, productive people, rather than to address all of the potential ways that our neighborhoods and cities can compromise the human experience.	2 <u>Imperative 07_Civilized environment</u> Having local food program, community hub, car and bike sharing programme, info center, community book library.
	3 <u>Imperative 08_Healthy neighbourhood design</u> Design features and strategies that promote and optimise the health and well-being of its residents (e.g. walking trails, plaza, playgrounds, ...). >> Access for residents and occupants to either dedicated walking trails, sidewalks or pedestrian paths directly accessible from every building.
	4 <u>Imperative 09_Biophilic environment</u> Integration of nature elements.
Equity Support a just and equitable world.	5 <u>Imperative 14_Human scale and human places</u> The project must be designed to create human-scaled rather than automobile-scaled places.
	6 <u>Imperative 15_Universal access to nature and place</u> Public spaces have to be fully accessible to all people. >> Access for those with physical disabilities must be safeguarded through designs meeting the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) and Architectural Barriers Act (ABA)
	7 <u>Imperative 16_Universal access to community services</u>

Services have to be fully accessible to all people. The basic community services and amenities to be considered are: shops, place to congregate, place to work, place to learn.

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 17. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [7].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Sociocultural and Functional Quality	1 <u>SOC 1.1 Thermal comfort in open spaces</u> The objective is to increase the attractiveness of public spaces by taking microclimatic effects into account during planning. This promotes a pleasant, varied climate in the district throughout the year, which meets the different individual thermal needs of users. >> considering the climatic conditions of the neighbourhood in terms of wind, solar radiation/temperatures, and shaded areas.
	2 <u>SOC 1.6 Open space</u> The objective is to satisfy the need for recreation, leisure, enjoyment of nature, exchange and interaction by providing high-quality open spaces within walking distance. >> Consider the integration into the urban context, the materials used, and the type of open space (e.g., square, playground, etc.). >> Equipment: Design specifications for handling street furniture (seating, bicycle parking, bus stops, etc.) >> Lighting: Design specifications for outdoor lighting beyond functional lighting and energy considerations
	3 <u>SOC 1.9 Noise, exhaust and light emissions/immissions</u> The objective is to reduce the effects of noise and light on people and to ensure clean air. Beyond the existing legal emission regulations, the lowest possible emissions should be generated
	4 <u>SOC 2.1 Barrier-free design</u> "Our objective is to make the entire environment accessible to everyone and without restrictions on its use, regardless of their personal condition" >> <u>Local facilities</u> 1. Education: Childcare and primary school max. walking distance 200m as the crow flies 2. Playgrounds max. walking distance 200m as the crow flies 3. Local supply 1: Full-range supplier (offer of goods for daily needs) max. walking distance 400 m as the crow flies 4. Local supply 2: Small-scale commercial retail (bakery, butcher, drugstore,...) max. walking distance 400 m as the crow flies 5. Medical facilities: General practitioner max. walking distance 400 m as the crow flies 6. Bus or tram stop: max. walking distance 200 m as the crow flies 7. Catering: Restaurant, café, canteen, dining hall, etc., max. walking distance 400 m as the crow flies 8. Sanitary facilities: Toilet for disabled people, max. walking distance 200 m as the crow flies >> <u>Barrier-free movement areas</u> 1. Width of movement area on footpaths in the vicinity of schools, childcare facilities, leisure and care facilities, shopping centres, pedestrian crossings and passages: 3 m 2. Width of the movement area of footpaths at the narrowest point (in road space and in open spaces): 1.5 m 3. Width of the movement area on side walkways, in passages at cash registers and controls: 0.9 m 4. Resting places in front of public facilities: 1.5 x 1.5 m (e.g., as turning possibility, as a relaxing or resting area, at the beginning and end of a ramp, in front of house and building entrances, etc.) 5. Movement area within footpaths: 2.0 x 2.5 m (after max. 18 m, within the visibility range) 6. Execute footpaths with a longitudinal gradient of 0-3 %, if necessary, with a gradient of 3-6 % only resting places at least every 10 m 7. Traffic-reduced road space: Orientation by means of tactile and optically contrasting guidance systems 8. Access, pedestrian crossing and passage with lowered pavement, perpendicular to the road, without visibility barriers 9. Different levels must be made accessible by means of DINcompliant ramps or lifts (possibly also escalator or moving walkway)

10. Barrier-free public transport stops (height differences and distances to be overcome ≤ 3 cm, marked entry points, weather protection, movement areas not crossed by bicycle paths)
11. Sufficient parking spaces for disabled persons (3 % of the parking spaces, but at least 1 parking space; 1.5 m deep movement area next to the long side for transverse parking, 7.5 m long and 2.5 m wide for longitudinal parking)
12. Sufficient car parking spaces for disabled people in the immediate vicinity of the arena (corresponding to the total capacity of the arena: 15,000 - 20,000 visitors = at least 30 wheelchair users + at least 10 visually impaired; 20,000 - 30,000 visitors = at least 50 wheelchair users + 12 visually impaired; 30,000 - 50,000 = at least 75 wheelchair users + at least 15 visually impaired; > 50,000 visitors = at least 100 wheelchair users + at least 20 visually impaired)

>> Visual information elements

1. Adherence to the prescribed contrasts for characters and symbols, especially with emergency and warning functions as well as for information carriers (special care with custom solutions!)
2. Implementation of uniform, glare-free ambient lighting with accentuated illumination of important areas (e.g. stairs) and possible targets (e.g. information boards)
3. Selection of helpful colour combinations of visual object and surroundings
4. Compliance with the minimum character size depending on the observer distance
5. Affixing and durability of visual information
6. Easy comprehensibility and clarity (use of easy language)
7. Semantic grouping (information elements with related content should be spatially grouped together)
8. Information elements that direct and accompany a movement process should form a continuous information chain

>> Spaces for disabled people

1. Sufficient seats and space for disabled people (according to the total capacity of the arena: 15,000 - 20,000 visitors = at least 30 wheelchair users + at least 10 visually impaired; 20,000 - 30,000 visitors = at least 50 wheelchair users + 12 visually impaired; 30,000 - 50,000 = at least 75 wheelchair users + at least 15 visually impaired; > 50,000 visitors = at least 100 wheelchair users + at least 20 visually impaired)
2. Seats and spaces are arranged separately, even, roofed, rainproof and have an unobstructed view
3. Seats and spaces are numbered, size according to E DIN 18040-1, with short and unobstructed access (easily accessible)
4. Seat for accompanying people, arranged laterally to the disabled seat
5. Seat for blind or visually impaired people with the possibility of auditory tracking of the event by radio transmission

5 SOC 3.1 Urban Design

The objective is to contribute cultural identity by establishing and maintaining consistent urban structure as part of the city as a whole

6 SOC 3.2 Social and functional mix

SOC 3.3 Social and commercial infrastructure

The objective is to make the district adaptable to social change, avoid segregation and gentrification and ensure a social and functional mix

Technical Quality 7 TEC 3.1 Mobility Infrastructure - Motorised Transportation

Design of public transport stops

1. Stop has roofing, lighting, seating, 2 points can be set per element
2. Dynamic stop information or additional (creative) stop element

8 TEC3.2 - Mobility Infrastructure - Pedestrians And Cyclists

Quality of bicycle parking facilities

1. The bicycle parking facility/ parking spaces are secured from theft and vandalism (min. 50 %)
2. The parking facility/parking spaces are protected from weather (min. 80 %)
3. The parking facility/parking spaces are lit up (min. 80 %)
4. For pedelecs and small electric vehicles (scooters, prams, ...) charging facilities are available in the form of parking spaces, charging cabinets for batteries, etc. (the number of charging facilities depends on a needs analysis)
5. Bicycle repair facility is accessible from 70% of the buildings within a ten minute walk (Weather-protected, well-illuminated and if necessary heated; The usual tools for bicycle repairs must be kept ready; A hand-washing basin)

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 18. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [8].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Wellbeing Joyful and healthful communities	1 <u>Active Living</u> 1. Improve access to open space. 2. Increase access to recreation facilities and programming. 3. Enhance walkability. 4. Expand safe and well-maintained cycling infrastructure."
	2 <u>Health</u> 1. Reduce incidents of community trauma. 2. Improve and create equitable access to nature."
	3 <u>Safety</u> Establish a feeling of safety in private and public spaces, in people's interaction with others, and their experience with services"
	4 <u>Parks and spaces</u> 1. Provide quality and accessible public spaces. 2. Increase access to public spaces, trails, and waterways. 3. Integrate nature and natural processes into public spaces"
Mobility Connected and accessible communities	5 <u>Street network</u> 1. Improve walkability throughout the community. 2. Accommodate people with disabilities to better move throughout the community by meeting ADA (Americans with Disabilities Act) and ABA (American Barriers Act) standards. 3. Adopt a complete streets strategy to encourage long-term street and sidewalk design investments"
	6 <u>Multimodality</u> 1. Establish safe pedestrian and bike facilities 2. Promote traffic calming to enhance safety and prioritization for bicyclists and pedestrians. 3. Improve connections between modes of travel"
	7 <u>Transit</u> 1. Provide high-quality, safe, and frequent public transit services. 2. Enhance speed and safety of transit throughout the community"

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 19. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [9].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
Health and Happiness Encouraging active, social, meaningful lives to promote good health and wellbeing	1 Access to green space and outdoor space
	2 Outdoor air quality (creating low-car neighbourhoods)
	3 Climate change adaptation
Equity and local economy Creating safe, equitable places to live and work which support local prosperity and international fair trade	4 Accessibility and inclusion (following universal design principles)
Culture and community Nurturing local identity and heritage, empowering communities and promoting a culture of sustainable living	5 Community facilities (e.g. repair cafés, library of things; spaces for temporary exhibition or open-air cinema)
	6 Safety and security (Secured by design)
Travel and transport Reducing the need to travel, encouraging walking, cycling and low-carbon transport	7 Provision of on-site facilities
	8 Design and safety of walking and cycling routes
	9 Promoting public transport
Land and nature Protecting and restoring land and marine systems for the benefit of people and wildlife	10 Integrating nature with public realm and buildings (incorporating a variety of habitats such as small areas of wildflowers, semi-scrub grass verges, wet ditches that incorporate sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS), log piles, bee planters and trees)

* Target user groups: all user groups (not specified)

Table 20. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [10].

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s)
A sense of control Having the ability to improve our area and address local problems can give us a sense of stability and security	1 Safety
Health equity All the living environments should equitably support communities to pursue healthy lifestyles, no matter where we live	2 Air, noise, light
Connection to nature The contact with nature is good for our mood and aids our recovery when we are ill, whether through interaction with our window boxes, local parks or countryside.	3 Green and blue spaces
	4 Biodiversity
	5 Climate resilience and adaptation
A sense of wonder Happiness, fun and wonder play an important role in our quality of life. The physical expression of this is seen in the design of our homes and neighbourhoods	6 Distinctive design (well-designed spaces)
	7 Play and recreation
Getting around There are significant health and wellbeing benefits to walking, wheeling and cycling, and public transport is crucial in maintaining equitable and resilient neighbourhoods	8 Walking, wheeling and cycling
	9 Public transport
Connected communities Local spaces need to enable a variety of social connections to emerge, while providing local job opportunities and a range of social services	10 Belonging (events; local social media group; ..)
	11 Local businesses and jobs (shops; cafes; working spaces; ..)
	12 Local services (community centers; schools; care services; ..)

* Target user groups: all user groups: people with disabilities, children, elderly and women are mentioned

Table 21. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [11] and relevant for the design and management of inclusive urban spaces.

Topic(s) *	Indicator(s) **
Proximity Services at a 5 min walking distance (e.g. 400-450 m)	1 Accessible services (e.g. shops, ..) and public spaces for socialisation
Safe walkability Infrastructure for safe and convenient walking and cycling	2 Pedestrian sidewalks and cycling paths of appropriate size and, if possible, physically separated or with slow zones >> It might be useful to consider several indicators of ergonomic design such as: 3 m width is sufficient for multiple users to have a conversation while walking, a wheelchair user needs 1,5 m to turn around and 1,8 to pass other wheel chairs, etc.
	3 Uninterrupted sidewalk network
	4 Safe crossings
	5 Clear and informative signage and signals, especially for pedestrian orientation (way-finding) >> It is also useful to provide areas with different colours, textured pavings, or tactile features
	6 Water management (e.g. green zones)
	7 Traffic calming measures to lower vehicle speed (30 km/h) in pedestrian areas (e.g. pinch-points, medians and refuge islands, speed humps, speed limits, vegetated buffers).
	8 Good street lighting
	9 Universally accessible pedestrian infrastructure

	10	Elements for passive surveillance (e.g. street retail) and mixed-use of the ground floors
	11	Place of respite (Places of enclosure (small areas, separated from the major activities of the street) provide places of respite from sensory information)
Green Areas	12	Green parks and community gardens
Urban green spaces facilitate the reduction of the heat island, reduce noise and air pollution	13	Green elements on the paths or greenery (e.g. green safety buffers, parklets)
Public transport	14	Elements for shading
Easy and universal access within 500m walking distance to low capacity public transport, and 1000m to high capacity public transport	15	Sitting areas
	16	Lighting for night-time use
	17	Waterpoints
Parking areas	18	Different car parking areas for different users' needs
Considering permeable or semi-permeable paving and porous surfaces	19	Secure bike parking areas

* Target user groups: all user groups: people with disabilities, children, elderly and women are mentioned.

** In the table, the topics and indicators merge different objectives and the core design recommendations that accelerate the achievement of the specific vision (named Principle). Meanwhile, the Tips are the design recommendation that supplements specific principles. In the table, these Tips are a bit different from the original document since they summarise "elements" regardless of city objectives.

Table 22. Summary of the main topics and indicators included in [12] and relevant for the design and management of inclusive urban spaces.

Critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements

Based on the described inclusion-exclusion process, the topics and indicators identified in each document were analysed and processed depending on their relevance in light of the research objectives. Document [2] was not taken into consideration as it did not provide any useful indicator, criteria or suggestion addressing specific physical elements of urban space.

Concerning [1], this process entailed the following actions:

- Four criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [6] [11] [23] [30].
- Nine were integrated by others: [1] by [5] [8] [13] [31]; [2] by [19] [21] [37]; [3] by [12] [24]; [4] by [34]; [7] by [15] [16] [26]; [9] by [17]; [10] by [39]; [20] by [32]; [22] by [39].
- Four were merged into two: [25] and [38]; [28] and [29].
- Three were excluded [18] [14] [27] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- One was excluded [33] as it concerns a specific equipment and not routes' accessibility.
- One was excluded as off-topic [35].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 23):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Accessible and usable pedestrian areas	i Provision of accessible pedestrian routes, particularly in relation to street crossings (e.g. absence of steps or presence of connecting ramps, acoustic signals, clear signage), including for accessing equipment.
	ii Provision of adequate wayfinding signage (e.g. directional and orientation signage, clearly legible text and numbers, adequate visual contrast, routes coded with different colour schemes).
	iii Presence of physical separation elements between pedestrian, cycling, and vehicular areas.
	iv Use of uniform, stable, and slip-resistant paving, ensuring adequate visual contrast and preventing water stagnation through drainage.
	v Provision of tactile ground surface indicators, particularly at intersections.
	vi Absence of obstacles or adequate marking of any obstacles, considering operating heights, maneuvering space, presence of vegetation.
	vii Provision of adequate lighting, uniform and designed to avoid direct or reflected glare.
	viii Provision of rest and seating areas along routes or within pedestrian areas.
	ix Provision of handrails for support and guidance on stepped routes, preferably on both sides of the path.
Urban furniture	x Provision of local public transport stops that are easy to identify, offer seating or support, and are adequately sheltered.
	xi Provision of bicycle parking facilities, easily identifiable and preferably covered.
	xii Provision of seating, designed in visual contrast with the surrounding environment and positioned so as not to obstruct pedestrian routes.
	xiii Presence of vegetative elements that also support orientation in open spaces.
Toilet facilities	xiv Provision of orientation maps (e.g. totems or tactile maps) to provide information and support wayfinding (e.g. in public parks or large pedestrian areas).
	xv Provision of accessible toilet facilities, clearly identifiable and appropriately signposted.

Table 23. Summary of the criteria identified in [1] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [3], this process entailed the following actions:

- Eight criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [1] [2] [3] [5] [6] [8] [11] [12].
- Four were excluded as off-topic [4] [7] [9] [10].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 24):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Social and economic wellbeing	i Delivery of services, facilities and amenities
	ii Public realm
	iii Microclimate
	iv Green Infrastructure
	v Inclusive Design
Transport and mobility	vi Safe and appealing streets
	vii Cycling facilities
	viii Public transport facilities

Table 24. Summary of the criteria identified in [3] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [4], the critical analysis led to the following actions:

- Two criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [6] [8].
- Three were excluded [1] [4] [9] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- One was excluded as off-topic [2] [3] [5] [7] [10] [11] [12] [13].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 25):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Society - Amenity	i Convenience/welfare
Economy - Traffic/Urban structure	ii Traffic

Table 25. Summary of the criteria identified in [4] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

In relation to [5], the operations performed entailed:

- Two criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [1] [3].
- One was excluded [2] as a generic action not precisely addressing a physical element in space.

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 26):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Neighbourhood organization and planning	i Pedestrian usability of streets
	ii Tree-lined avenues and shaded streets

Table 26. Summary of the criteria identified in [5] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

When addressing [6], the following procedure was undertaken:

- One criteria was defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [5].
- Six were excluded [1] [2] [3] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space or because off-topic [4] [6] [7].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 27):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Connectivity	i Streets

Table 27. Summary of the criteria identified in [6] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [7], this process entailed the following actions:

- Three criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [1] [3] [6].
- Two were excluded [5] [7] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- Two were excluded as off-topic [2] [4].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 28):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Place	i Human-powered living
Health and happiness	ii Healthy neighbourhood design
Equity	iii Universal access to nature and place

Table 28. Summary of the criteria identified in [7] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [8], the critical analysis led to the following actions:

- Four criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [2] [4] [7] [8].
- Two were excluded [1] [3] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- Two were excluded as off-topic [5] [6].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 29):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Sociocultural and functional quality	i Open space
	ii Barrier-free design
Technical quality	iii Mobility infrastructure – motorised transportation
	iv Mobility infrastructure – pedestrians and cyclists

Table 29. Summary of the criteria identified in [8] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

In relation to [9], the operations performed entailed:

- One criteria was defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [5].
- Four was excluded [1] [4] [6] [7] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- Two were excluded as off-topic [2] [3].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 30):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Mobility	i Streets network

Table 30. Summary of the criteria identified in [9] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

When addressing [10], the following procedure was undertaken:

- Two criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [4] [7].
- Two were excluded [5] [10] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- Six were excluded as off-topic [1] [2] [3] [6] [8] [9].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 31):

Topic(s)	Criteria *
Equity and local economy	i Accessibility and inclusion
Travel and transport	ii Provision of on-site facilities

* the document explicitly refers to external technical references providing thorough guidance for the design of physical elements fostering accessibility

Table 31. Summary of the criteria identified in [10] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [11], this process entailed the following actions:

- Three criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [3] [8] [9].
- Two were excluded [2] [6] as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space.
- Seven were excluded as off-topic [1] [4] [5] [7] [10] [11] [12].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 32):

Topic(s)	Criteria
Connection to nature	i Green and blue spaces
Getting around	ii Walking, wheeling and cycling
	iii Public transport

Table 32. Summary of the criteria identified in [11] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Concerning [12], the critical analysis led to the following actions:

- Fourteen criteria were defined as relevant specifications and maintained in their original form [2] [3] [4] [5] [7] [8] [9] [11] [14] [15] [16] [17] [18] [19]
- Three were excluded as generic actions not precisely addressing a physical element in space [1] [12] [13].
- Two were excluded as off-topic [6] [10].

This led to the following criteria to be selected (Table 33):

Topic(s)	Indicator(s)
Proximity and walkability in complete streets Elements that provide comfort of use, safety and security	i Pedestrian sidewalks and cycling paths have an appropriate size
	ii Sidewalk networks are uninterrupted
	iii There are safe crossings
	iv There are clear and informative signage and signals, especially for pedestrian orientation
	v There are traffic calming measures to lower vehicle speed in pedestrian areas (e.g. pinch-points, medians and refuge islands, speed humps, vegetated buffers)
	vi Good street lighting is provided
	vii There is a universally accessible pedestrian infrastructure
	viii There are places of respite
Accessible public transport stops	ix Shadings structures are provided
	x There are comfortable sitting areas
	xi Lighting for night-time use is good
	xii There are water points
Places of attraction	xiii Environment for socialising are provided (e.g. seating and resting areas, green spaces as parklets)
	xiv Secure bike parking areas are available

Table 33. Summary of the criteria identified in [12] that the critical analysis considered relevant and pertaining to the investigation objective.

Overall, a total of 55 criteria referring to precise physical elements of the built environment increasing the usability and accessibility of urban spaces was identified.

By examining each of them, 15 specific features for which specifications could be provided were clustered and the related target user groups were defined. Table 34 in the next page summarises both the features and the individuals that would benefit most from their implementation in the built environment.

The last part of the investigation was devoted to developing a set of specifications to communicate accessibility-related relevant information to stakeholders acting on the design and management of the outdoor built environment. Starting from the criteria, the “Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces: Design Guidelines” were drawn and included in [Annex DS4_RT2.4.1-A2](#).

Inclusive physical features	Target user groups				
	People with motor impairments	People with visual impairments	People with hearing impairments	People with mild cognitive impairments	Elderly people
Artificial lighting	•	•	•	•	•
Bicycle parking					•
Connecting ramps	•	•			•
Dividing elements	•	•	•	•	•
LOGES system		•			
Orientation maps	•	•	•	•	•
Other orientation elements	•	•	•	•	•
Paving	•	•		•	•
Public toilets	•	•	•	•	•
Public transport stops	•	•	•	•	•
Seats (and respite areas)	•	•	•	•	•
Supporting handrails	•	•			
Traffic lights and safe crossing	•	•	•	•	•
Wayfinding		•	•	•	•
Water points (and other small urban elements)	•	•	•	•	•

Table 34. “Physical features” to implement in neighbourhood for improving usability and accessibility in urban open spaces, defined based on the prompts emerging from the reviewed and analysed documents, and related target user groups.

2.6. OUTPUTS

The following outputs were developed, reported here according to the action they refer to:

Comparative assessment of the existing mobile apps.

Outputs of this activity are: (i) a structured framework detailing the features of 24 existing apps supporting navigation in urban areas, including and organising a dataset concerning both general and accessibility-related information (Annex DS4_RT2.4.1-A1); and (ii) a subset of 5 applications presenting features relevant for pedestrian accessibility for people with motor impairments in built environments, also suitable for carrying out the subsequent user-centered evaluation.

Comprehensive analysis of design-relevant aspects of mobility apps for inclusive urban mobility.

The output of this activity is a set of issues and limitations in existing applications supporting urban navigation, developed into comprehensive recommendations to improve usability and accessibility in the built environment.

User-centred evaluation of accessibility features in urban mobility apps.

The output of this activity is a set of user-based findings describing the strengths, limitations, and improvement needs of the apps' features to improve pedestrian accessibility for people with motor impairments in urban areas.

Review of current tools, documents and protocols.

Output of this activity is a structured framework identifying and categorising all criteria, suggestions, tips or indicators ("indicators") and the related thematic areas ("topics") provided by 12 existing frameworks - tools, documents and protocols - and aiming at improving quality of life in urban areas.

Critical analysis of reviewed frameworks and related design elements.

Outputs of this activity are: (i) a reference framework, deriving from the previous one, including a set of specifications targeted at improving accessibility and usability of urban spaces at the neighbourhood scale for individuals with mild impairments and elderly, and (ii) a set of design recommendations and guiding principles highlighting specific physical elements to be implemented in the built environment. These outputs were further developed and incorporated into guidelines: "Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces: design guidelines" (Annex DS4_RT2.4.1-A2). The aim of this document is to communicate accessibility- and usability-related information to stakeholders involved in the design and management of urban areas, guiding them in making public spaces more inclusive, especially for people with disabilities and older adults. It is conceived as a toolkit providing a checklist of relevant physical elements to address, and it targets end users such as urban planners, designers, developers, and public administrations.

3. CORRELATION WITH THE CASCADE FUNDED PROJECTS

During [Milestone 2](#) and [Milestone 3](#), two cascade funding calls were activated to support the realisation of innovative research projects, connecting the topics addressed by the Spoke 4 activities with the local territory's productive fabric. The first call projects started in May 2024, while the second call ones in November 2024. All funded projects were expected to close their research activities by November 2025.

As reported in [DS4_RT2.1.1](#), three projects of the first call and four of the second have been monitored by the team members involved in RT2.1 and RT2.4 to provide technical-scientific support and to verify that the activities complied with the ongoing work plan. These projects respectively fall into the scope of activities RT2.1 "New materials and devices" ([Milestone 3](#)):

- "Construction Agile 5.0" (CoA5.0).
- "Murano Design for filtering concrete in urban regeneration initiatives" (EKONYA).
- "Non Si Butta Via Niente" (NSBVN).
- "Eco-friendly retrofit for existing buildings with engineered wood structures" (RECOFIT).
- "PAssive hybRid Systems maximizing wind powER in the enviroNment of uRban settlements" (PARSEOR).
- "Revero Murano - implementation of an innovative and sustainable process to upcycle non-recyclable glass waste" (Re_MU).

and 2.4 "Living, usability, accessibility" ([Milestone 4](#)):

- "Inclusive Domotic Environment for the Aged people" (IDEA).

The monitoring was conducted through monthly online meetings involving both researchers and project partners, and continued until the end of Milestone 4. The meetings aimed to verify that the activities implemented, the documents delivered, and the intermediate and final results comply with the research programme, while the potential impacts on the territory are illustrated in [DS4_RM4](#) and [DS4_RT2.6.3](#). A brief summary of activities conducted in each project and related results is reported below, with a focus on IDEA - the one in line with RT2.4 research..

Pilot project CoA 5.0

"Construction Agile 5.0" (May 2024 - Nov 2025) addressed the improvement of the building process management to develop a method interconnecting the design phase, the construction one and the delivered building monitoring. To achieve this result, the project integrated the activities of all the actors involved in the supply chain related to a building by delivering an innovative methodology based and developing a shared software cloud platform allowing for co-design through all phases of the construction - a process tested in two pilot building sites.

Pilot Project EKONYA

"Murano design for filtering concrete in urban regeneration initiatives" (May 2024 - Nov 2025) intended to develop an external paving solution suited for roadside strips, bicycle paths and pedestrian areas merging a high potential of water drainage and filtering of heavy metals with the valorisation of scraps in the perspective of industrial symbiosis. To reach this objective, an innovative material concrete-based (geopolymer) was developed that acts by two filtering levels, a chemical and a mechanical one. The prototype was then tested and validated.

Pilot Project NSBVN

"Nonsibuttavianiente" (May 2024 - Nov 2025) promoted the application of circular economy principles in the natural stone-based products manufacturing, by defining and testing a method for optimising the production of the pieces that allow to reduce the scraps and to recycle the slawing sludge, currently a waste of the process. The project developed a design

process that allows to maximise simultaneously the three aspects of material efficiency, production timeframes, and cost-effectiveness ratio. This process was tested in the design and production of both a materially optimised marble-based collection and a “neo-material” developed valorising the waste produced.

Pilot Project RECOFIT

“Eco-friendly retrofit for existing buildings with engineered wood structures” (Nov 2024 - Nov 2025) aimed to develop innovative and sustainable solutions for the renovation sector, using engineered wood construction systems for the reuse and retrofit of the existing building stock, offering significant advantages in terms of environmental sustainability, energy efficiency and costs reduction. Based on the definition of the wood species, the analysis of possible application areas and the design of a structural, reversible and dry-assembled module, the project developed and validated an innovative wood-based constructive system, testing its effectiveness by the installation of prototypes on existing buildings.

Pilot Project PARSEOR

“Passive hybrid Systems maximizing wind power in the environment of urban settlements” (Nov 2024 - Nov 2025) addressed the possibility of taking advantage of wind turbulence in urban areas by an ad-hoc developed microeolic system. This included the aerodynamic and mechanical design, prototyping, and testing of the wind turbine, developed with the use of sustainable materials. Data management aspects related to urban wind energy generation were carried out to comply with automated pre-processing for techno-economic assessment and post-processing activities for remote monitoring, introducing an innovative prototype based on machine learning and Urban Wind Community learning, supporting data sharing for both energy production and citizen science applications related to urban wind dynamics and climate change impacts. The full system integration with all devised components was then tested in pilot applications and the device was also validated in compliance with relevant EU Regulations.

Pilot Project Re_MU

“Revero-Murano” (Nov 2024 - Nov 2025) aimed to implement a process to revalorize non-recyclable glass waste into high-quality mono-material surfaces, giving new life to waste otherwise destined for landfill. A feasibility study of the industrial process of waste revalorization was carried out, providing the basis for the prototyping and validating machinery and processes in an industrially relevant environment. The technology developed in the project will enable the scaling up of the process developed by the start-up rehub, which works on transforming waste glass into a moldable paste at room temperature, and which will be used to make innovative surfaces for sectors such as fashion, furniture, design and construction.

Pilot pilot project IDEA

Cascade-funded research project “Inclusive Domotic Environment for the Aged people” (Nov 2024 - Nov 2025) aimed to improve the autonomy and quality of life of elderly individuals through the implementation of innovative home automation solutions as well as supporting the regeneration of inhabited spaces. Thus, although addressing interior spaces, its objective and scope were closely related to RT2.4 scope and actions.

Starting from the analysis of the needs of the elderly and their caregivers and a survey concerning home automation solutions, the objective was to identify the most appropriate technical and digital solutions to be implemented into a prototype system supporting elderly

care, reducing burdens on caregivers and increasing users' autonomy, improving their overall well-being and safety.

The research activities were carried out according to a three-step structure:

- Definition of the state of the art and identification of the design prerequisites.
- Design of all the components necessary for the creation of the prototype solution.
- Development, testing and validation of the components developed, including installations in trial sites, paying particular attention to the acceptance of the technology by the elderly subjects and to the degree of actual improvement of the care service by the operators.

The focus on the design criteria provided the methodological and functional foundations for the following phases. Building on these, an integrated hardware and software system was defined to support assisted independent living for older adults. The modular hardware architecture incorporates environmental sensing, video surveillance, video communication, and monitoring of vital parameters, with careful selection of components suitable for deployment in trial settings. In parallel, a mobile application was designed to enable remote monitoring, voice interaction, and alert management through an accessible and intuitive interface. Additionally, a web-based dashboard was developed for control centre operators, offering advanced tools for data management, alert visualisation, historical data analysis, and support to therapeutic activities.

Laboratory testing was carried out to validate individual components and an initial integrated prototype. The system was then installed in the pilot locations and integrated within the existing software ecosystem. The solution was tested under real operational conditions, with particular attention to the usability and effectiveness of the mobile app and dashboard. The evaluation confirmed the prototype's functional reliability and its compliance with actual needs of caregivers, field operators, and control centre personnel.

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ANNEXES

Spoke 4

CITY, ARCHITECTURE,
AND SUSTAINABLE
DESIGN

**Leader: Università
Iuav di Venezia**

Research Topic

RT2

Technological solutions for the
construction and sustainable
design sectors

DS4_RT2.4.1-A1

Structured framework of
existing apps supporting
inclusive navigation in
urban environments with
detail of their inclusive
services and contents

APPS		GENERAL INFORMATION																INCLUSIVITY-RELATED INFORMATION																								
No.	APP name	Store Category	Store		Issue Date	Last Update	App Version	Available for free	Mobile / Web		Participatory / Consultative		Geographical coverage		Use of maps				Overall rating per Store (stars/ratings)			Downloads	Services provided							End user targeted (impairment)			APP Native Interaction Modality INPUT				APP Native Interaction Modality OUTPUT					
			Coogle Play Store	Apple Store					Mobile-App	Web App	Participatory	Consultative	Area of application	Real Coverage	Coogle Maps	Mapbox	Open Street Map	Maps (Apple)	Coogle Play Store	Apple Store	On-line Navigation		POIs	Accessible route	Accessible POI	Route preview	AR features	User report	Mild cognitive	Motor	Visual	Audio	Camera	Text	Touch	Audio	Tactile	Video				
1	Maps AR	Travel and local info	●		08/2015	11/2023	2.1.1	●	●		●		Worldwide		●				N/A	N/A	1000+	●	●			●						●	●	●		●	●	●				
2	Kimap	Maps and navigation	●	●	06/2017	08/2024	3.01.01	●	●	●	●	Worldwide	Many cities not mapped		●	●			4,1/38	4,7/12	1000+		●	●								●	●			●						
3	Omniaroad	Maps and navigation	●		08/2023	02/2025	9.0.0	●	●		●	Worldwide	Four IT cities only	N/A				N/A	N/A	50+						●											●					
4	WeGlad	Travel and local info	●	●	08/2021	01/2025	4.1.5	●	●		●	Italy		●				N/A	4,9/10	1000+ (GPS)																	●					
5	Wheelmap	Travel and local info	●	●	03/2012	12/2024	5.4	●	●	●	●	Worldwide			●	●			4,4/769	4,0/3	50.000+		●														●					
6	Roll Mobility	Travel and local info	●		12/2020	02/2025	2.1290	●	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				N/A	N/A	10.000+																		●				
7	OsmAnd	Maps and navigation	●	●	08/2010	04/2025	5.0.5	●	●	●	●	Worldwide				●		N/A	N/A	N/A		●	●	●	●									●			●					
8	Mapillary	Maps and navigation	●		06/2021	05/2025	6.8.28	●	●	●	●	Worldwide				●		3,7/858	N/A	10.000+																		●				
9	Google Maps	Maps and navigation	●		02/2005	04/2025	765881323	●	●	●	●	Worldwide		●				3,6/18Min	N/A	10Mid+		●	●	●	●	●												●				
10	Maps	Maps and navigation			N/A	N/A	N/A	●	●	●	●	Worldwide					●	N/A	2,7/2.221	N/A		●		●														●				
11	Route4U	Navigation	●	●	04/2025	10/2025	2.8.1	●	●		●	Worldwide	Few countries only		●	●		4,0/5	N/A	1000+		●	●	●	●													●				
12	EasyWay Public Transport	Navigation Travel and local info	●	●	N/A	03/2025	6.11.5	●	●		●	UKR, BG, HR, GR, MD, RS, TU	Major cities across countries	●				4,4/93.453	4,6/25	1Min+		●	●	●	●													●				
13	Scotland transport Wheelchair	Navigation Travel and local info	●	●	N/A	06/2021	?	●	●		●	Scotland (UK)			●	●		N/A	N/A	100+		●	●	●	●													●				
14	DeQua	Navigation	●	●	12/2022	01/2024	1.2.4	●	●		●	Venice (IT)				●		5,0/14	5,0/7	1000+		●	●	●														●				
15	WheeLog!	Maps and navigation Motor assist.	●	●	05/2017	04/2024	3.04.02	●	●	●	●	Worldwide	Japan mainly	●				4,8/5	N/A	10.000+		●	●	●		●	●											●				
16	On wheels	Travel and local info	●	●	04/2015	09/2024	3.0.1	●	●		●	Flanders (BE)	Seven cities					3,0/9	5,0/1	5000+	Not understandable																			●		
17	Urbi	Travel and local info	●	●	N/A	N/A	6.17	●	●		●	Europe and USA		●				2,9/968	3,9/155	100.000+	Position of shared vehicles only																				●	
18	WheelMate	Navigation		●	01/2013	01/2021	1.0.8	●	●	●	●	Worldwide		●				N/A	4,7/6	17.000+	Not working																			●		
19	Lazarillo	Navigation	●	●	09/2016	02/2025	2.7.2	●	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				4,8/1.715	2,8/5	100.000+	●	●																		●		
20	GoodMaps outdoor	Maps and navigation	●	●	11/2022	04/2024	5.1.1	●	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				N/A	N/A	1000+	●	●																		●		
21	Soundscape	Navigation		●	N/A	N/A	1.2	●	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				N/A	4,6/41	N/A		●																		●		
22	NaviLens	Tools	●		N/A	N/A	5.0.12	●	●		N/A		Worldwide		N/A				N/A	N/A	50.000+	Navigation through QR code																		●		
23	Moovit	Navigation	●	●	N/A	03/2025	5.164.0.1700	●*	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				3,5/1Min	4,5/39.043	865Min+ (AS) 100Min+ (GPS)		●																		●		
24	Be my eyes	Styles and Trends	●	●	N/A	N/A	N/A	●	●		●	Worldwide		N/A				4,4/31.328	4,8/460	1Min+	Remote assistance only																					●

(*) Free application, but with advertising
▲ App not specifically designed for people with disabilities, but useful for those who need to know the condition of the road surface, sidewalks, steps, and pedestrian crossings.

Spoke 4

CITY, ARCHITECTURE,
AND SUSTAINABLE
DESIGN

**Leader: Università
Iuav di Venezia**

Research Topic

RT2

Technological solutions for the
construction and sustainable
design sectors

DS4_RT2.4.1-A2

Inclusive physical features
improving the usability
and accessibility of urban
spaces: design guidelines

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1. GLOSSARY

Ageing

At the biological level, ageing results from the impact of the accumulation of a wide variety of molecular and cellular damage over time. This leads to a gradual decrease in physical and mental capacity, a growing risk of disease and ultimately death. These changes are neither linear nor consistent, they are only loosely associated with a person's age in years and are strongly influenced by the environment and behaviours of the individual. Common conditions in older age include hearing loss, cataracts and refractive errors, back and neck pain and osteoarthritis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, diabetes, depression and dementia. As people age, they are more likely to experience several conditions at the same time (WHO, 2015).

Elderly people

Based on both the United Nations (2025) and the WHO (2025) they can be defined as those who have reached the age of 60 years and over. This definition is relevant within the ageing context.

End users

The expected users of the existing documents, tools or protocols examined in these guidelines, stakeholders that range from Public Administrations and institutional bodies to developers, planners, construction businesses, designers or the communities dwelling a neighbourhood themselves.

Innovative solutions

Physical solutions allowing an inclusive fruition of urban space, meant as inclusive means of designing and/or managing physical systems and infrastructure fell within it.

Older persons

See: Elderly people

PEBA

Piano di Eliminazione per le Barriere Architettoniche (*Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers*), introduced in the Italian legislation by Law 41/1986 and mandatory for all public bodies managing buildings and spaces open to the public to ensure their accessibility.

People/individuals with motor impairments

Individuals who experience limitations in movement, coordination, or physical functioning due to conditions affecting the musculoskeletal system, nervous system, or both. Characteristics to be considered include: reduced strength, speed, endurance, or coordination; difficulty with mobility, posture, or manipulation of objects. The impairment may be congenital or acquired (WHO, 2001; UN, 2006).

People/individuals with visual impairments

Individuals who have a reduction in vision that cannot be fully corrected with standard glasses, contact lenses, medication, or surgery. Characteristics to be considered include: blindness, low vision, reduced visual acuity, visual field loss, or contrast sensitivity loss. The impairment may be congenital or acquired (UN, 2006; WHO, 2001, 2022).

People/individuals with hearing impairments

Individuals who experience partial or total inability to hear in one or both ears, affecting their ability to perceive sounds and understand speech. Characteristics to be considered include

ranges from mild hearing loss to profound deafness. The impairment may be congenital or acquired (UN, 2006; WHO, 2001, 2022).

People/individuals with mild cognitive impairments

Individuals who experience a measurable decline in one or more cognitive domains that is greater than expected for age, but does not significantly interfere with independent daily functioning. Cognitive domains may include: memory, attention, executive function, language, visuospatial skills (UN, 2006; WHO, 2001, 2022).

Target user groups

With reference to the current document: people with motor impairments, people with visual impairments, people with hearing impairments, people with mild cognitive impairments, elderly people.

Vulnerable people/individuals

Elderly and people with mild physical impairments. Individuals with serious disabilities or cognitive problems are therefore excluded from this definition.

Urban space

With reference to the current document: exterior places of urban areas in which usability and accessibility can be improved by properly designing or managing the built environment at a neighbourhood scale, enabling ease of navigation and fostering social inclusion by considering routes, services and points of interest (POIs).

2. SUMMARY AND MAIN RECOMMENDATIONS

The aim of this document is to provide a reference framework for inclusive physical features - namely, design elements and urban furniture - improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces for individuals with mild physical and/or sensory impairments and older adults. In particular, the target user groups considered for this study are: (a) people with motor impairments, (b) people with visual impairments, (c) people with hearing impairments, (d) people with mild cognitive impairments, and (e) elderly people.

The focus of these guidelines is at the neighbourhood level, including routes, services, open spaces, points of interest (POIs) and physical features. In fact, specific physical elements in the built environment can enable people to experience urban spaces safely and comfortably, thereby enhancing their psychophysical well-being.

The document is structured in two main sections. The first section proposes a review of existing tools, documents and protocols supporting inclusive urban areas, from which suggestions and elements to be considered in the design and management of urban spaces can be drawn. These documents pertain to three different domains: (i) European and National standards, (ii) manuals of sustainability assessment frameworks at the neighbourhood scale, (iii) other relevant international documents and tools. Their analysis allowed defining for each document a list of elements and specifications affecting inclusive liveability and usability of urban spaces.

The second section presents a reference framework developed through a critical analysis based on the data retrieved in the review of existing documents. By clustering the several recurring elements emerged from the analysis, it provides a structured identification of a series of physical features to be considered for this document's purposes, identifies the specific target user groups on which they positively impact, and supplies a comprehensive description merging the relevant information retrieved.

All the references, divided according to the thematic content, are provided at the end of the document.

This document can be considered as a guide for several end users that aim to improve the usability and accessibility of urban spaces for individuals with mild physical and/or sensory impairments and older adults. Nevertheless, all the elements and specifications it includes are to be considered as means to enhance the inclusivity of public spaces in general terms, far beyond the ageing and impairments domains.

The document structure can act as a checklist: by understanding the purpose and features of the listed elements and verifying their existence in urban spaces or implementing them, it is possible to improve the built environment and ensure the health and well-being of the people who live in it, especially the specific target user groups. This document, originally developed for the Italian context, can be used in conjunction with other existing tools (e.g. the Italian PEBAs), and is intended to be a first step in this direction.

3. EXISTING TOOLS, DOCUMENTS AND PROTOCOLS SUPPORTING INCLUSIVE URBAN AREAS: A REVIEW

Indeed, the environment we live and move in has a significant impact on our perception of space, autonomy, and overall comfort and well-being (Gehl, 1987), particularly for individuals with disabilities and the elderly (van Dijk et al., 2015). Therefore, recognising and overcoming urban obstacles (architectural barriers) is not enough to guarantee environmental accessibility and inclusion. The outdoor urban space needs other physical - as well as social - characteristics, since accessibility is “a collective resource that can elevate the social capital of a community” (Lauria, 2017, p. 57). More accessible environments expand individual freedom, social opportunities, and knowledge; at the same time, they can be more attractive, comfortable, communicative, and safe (Lauria, 2017, p. 57), in line with the 2030 Agenda’s Sustainable Development Goal n. 11, “Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable” (UN, 2015).

As understanding which specific physical features should be considered and integrated into urban spaces appears fundamental, the following review of 12 existing tools, documents and protocols was carried out to support the identification process. The selection of the references was based on their primary objective and the context in which they are applied (urban areas and neighbourhoods). All of them aspire to pursue sustainability in its different domains; nevertheless, only issues specifically pertaining to the social dimension of sustainability have been analysed, as the ones more strictly related to the document scope and aim. The reviewed tools, documents and protocols can be divided in three groups:

1. Two European and National standards and documents, more specifically the UNI EN CEI 172010:2021 and “Linee Guida interdisciplinari per la redazione del PEBA della Regione Emilia-Romagna”. As they set out the standards for environmental accessibility and inclusion in urban areas within the Italian context, they provide the basis for the analysis.
2. Eight open-access manuals of National and International frameworks developed to perform Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessments (NSA tools), namely: BREEAM Communities, CASBEE-UD, GBC Quartieri, EcoDistrict, Living Community Challenge, DGNB Districts, Just Communities, One Planet Living. These tools and protocols operate at the neighbourhood scale and are useful for evaluating the extent to which new constructions or redevelopments pursue environmental, economic and social sustainability.
3. Two international documents and tools, My Neighbourhood by UN-Habitat and the Quality of Life Framework. The first one was drafted by one of the most influential international bodies, while the second represents an evolution of one of the previously cited NSA tools. They both aim to improve people’s quality of life in urban spaces.

In some cases, the examined documents explicitly identify the target user groups, with particular emphasis on individuals with disabilities and/or vulnerable ones. This concerns both the National and European standards [1] and the other two international documents [3]. The following paragraphs report the topics and indicators set out by each reference that are most relevant to this document’s objectives, also providing a brief comment about the possible potential and criticalities identified in the documents.

3.1. National and European documents and standards

Issues related to environmental accessibility and inclusion in urban spaces are closely linked to standards and regulations for recognising and overcoming urban obstacles (architectural barriers) in the built environment. In this sense, although they have some positive aspects, Italian national standards – Legge 13/1989 and Decreto Ministeriale 236/1989 – are quite dated. Nevertheless, two documents can support the pursuit of inclusive design principles in National and European areas:

- The UNI EN CEI 17210:2021 standard, which transposes the European EN 17210:2021 *Accessibility and usability of the built environment – Functional requirements one*.
- The *Linee Guida interdisciplinari per la redazione del PEBA della Regione Emilia-Romagna (Emilia-Romagna Region interdisciplinary guidelines for the PEBA drafting)*.

The UNI standard (UNI, 2021) is a fundamental reference based on the Design for All and Universal Design approaches and describes the basic functional requirements and recommendations for an accessible and usable built environment. Its main aim is to promote the equitable and safe use of the built environment for as many people as possible, including those with disabilities. This standard can be applied to the design, redevelopment and/or adaptation of the built environment, both indoors and outdoors. While the recommendations are formulated qualitatively, all the requirements enable the various end users (public authorities, developers, designers, ...) to precisely understand how to achieve inclusion objectives and promote well-being in different living spaces. Each application area – such as accessible and usable pedestrian areas and urban furniture, to name one – presents its own set of main objectives, which are explained in detail. Examples and schemes are provided to help clarify how to pursue these objectives and to list the physical characteristics that the considered environment should have.

Although the second document (Regione Emilia-Romagna and CERPA, 2024) was developed by a Regional body and is not compulsory, it can be considered a relevant and innovative guidance document. In fact, it was conceived to provide a methodological support in drafting the “Piani per l’Eliminazione delle Barriere Architettoniche” (PEBAs, *Plans for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers*) also in other Italian regions and municipalities, as it outlines the key areas of application of a PEBA and the stages for its development and monitoring. However, the performed analysis reveals it is not particularly useful for this document’s purpose, since it does not provide detailed information, especially regarding urban elements and furniture.

Table 01 summarises the topics emerging from the analysis and that will be considered in this study. As mentioned above, the UNI standard is the most important reference for identifying the main physical elements that improve people’s quality of life in urban spaces. Its data was therefore considered as the basis for implementing the framework “Inclusive physical features improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces”.

Document	Year	Area	Identified topics and indicators
UNI EN CEI 172010 Accessibilità e usabilità dell'ambiente costruito – Requisiti funzionali*	2021	IT	<p>Accessible and usable pedestrian areas</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provision of an accessible pedestrian route, particularly in relation to street crossings (e.g. absence of steps or presence of connecting ramps, acoustic signals, clear signage), including for accessing equipment.). 2. Provision of adequate wayfinding signage (e.g. directional and orientation signage, clearly legible text and numbers, sufficient visual contrast, routes coded with different colour schemes). 3. Presence of physical separation elements between pedestrian, cycling, and vehicular areas. 4. Use of uniform, stable, and slip-resistant paving, ensuring adequate visual contrast and preventing water stagnation through drainage. 5. Provision of tactile ground surface indicators, particularly at intersections. 6. Absence of obstacles or adequate marking of any obstacles, considering operating heights, maneuvering space, presence of vegetation. 7. Provision of adequate lighting, uniform and designed to avoid direct or reflected glare. 8. Provision of rest and seating areas along routes or within pedestrian areas. 9. Provision of handrails for support and guidance on stepped routes, preferably on both sides of the path. <p>Urban furniture</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. Provision of local public transport stops that are easy to identify, offer seating or support, and are adequately sheltered. 11. Provision of bicycle parking facilities, easily identifiable and preferably covered. 12. Provision of seating, designed in visual contrast with the surrounding environment and positioned so as not to obstruct pedestrian routes. 13. Presence of vegetative elements that also support orientation in open spaces. 14. Provision of orientation maps (e.g. totems or tactile maps) to provide information and support wayfinding (e.g. in public parks or large pedestrian areas). <p>Toilet facilities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Provision of accessible toilet facilities, clearly identifiable and appropriately signposted.
Linee Guida interdisciplinari per la redazione del PEBA della Regione Emilia-Romagna	2024	IT	<p><i>Note: although this is an innovative document fostering urban accessibility in the National context, it does not provide detailed information but only identifies the main areas of application of a PEBA, the stages for its drafting and monitoring.</i></p>

(*) The topics are related to application areas, listing different good practices useful in pursuing accessibility and usability objectives. The text was translated from the Italian version of the standard and could differ from the EN original text.

Table 01. A summary of the main topics and indicators emerging from the analysis of the national and European documents and standards.

3.2. Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment (NSA) frameworks

Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment (NSA) tools are voluntary and for-profit systems used to certify the performance of the urban built environment in terms of sustainability. They are developed by independent agencies and used to design and/or monitor specific urban areas when operating. Most of the tools developed at neighbourhood scale aim to quantify the environmental, social and economic impacts of residential, industrial or commercial areas, and can be applied for both new construction and redevelopment. NSA tools make it possible to “measure the sustainability of cities” by adopting a multi-criteria evaluation system. They are particularly relevant since neighbourhoods are the right scale for accommodating and experimenting with actions for sustainable urban development, while also promoting relationships between their residents (Sharifi et al., 2021).

In line with the objectives of the developed framework, issues related to social sustainability have been identified and analysed in the eight selected NSA tools. Social sustainability is linked to social equity and participation, urban safety and liveability, and quality of life (Shirazi and Keivani, 2019). In its domain it is possible to distinguish “hard” components, such as services, urban furniture, and transportation, from “soft” ones, including social interaction, culture, community, and participation, which are influenced by the former (Janssen et al., 2021). The integration of these themes in NSA tools is quite recent and still presents some difficulties (Attaianese & Acierno, 2017), this becomes clear when considering that accessibility is usually mentioned as a regulatory requirement rather than a key indicator of social inclusion.

Table 02 lists eight open-access NSA tools by year, organised from the oldest to the newest, and reports the geographical area of reference together with the main topics or indicators related to the “hard” components of social sustainability.

The screening revealed that the listed topics and indicators generally refer to three main areas: (i) quality of urban open spaces, streets, green areas, and urban furniture; (ii) transport quality and related facilities; and (iii) shared services for active living. The reported elements are always explained through qualitative definitions which establish whether a certain indicator is present, rather than referring to the physical qualities of specific elements in the urban space. Among the analysed NSA tools, only the DGNB Districts one provides more detailed information on physical elements, as the “Barrier-free design” and “Mobility infrastructure” indicators prove: in the first case, all specifications regarding reachability and manoeuvring space are provided, while, in the second, transport stops and bicycle parking facilities are described in detail, including their required design qualities. Nevertheless, the overall analysis has been useful in understanding which elements are considered valuable for creating socially inclusive open spaces and integrating them into urban planning and management processes.

Tool	Year	Area	Main topics and indicators
BREEAM Communities	2012 (rev. 2017)	UK	Social and economic wellbeing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Delivery of services, facilities and amenities ii. Public realm iii. Microclimate iv. Green infrastructure v. Inclusive design Transport and mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> vi. Safe and appealing streets vii. Cycling facilities viii. Public transport facilities
CASBEE-UD*	2014	JP	Society Amenity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Convenience/welfare Economy Traffic/Urban structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. Traffic
GBC Quartieri**	2015	IT	Neighbourhood organization and planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Pedestrian usability of streets ii. Tree-lined avenues and shaded streets
EcoDistrict	2018	US	Connectivity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Streets
Living Community Challenge	2019	US	Place <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Human-powered living Health and happiness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. Healthy neighbourhood design Equity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. Universal access to nature and place
DGNB-Districts	2020	DE	Sociocultural and functional quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Open space ii. Barrier-free design Technical quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. Mobility infrastructure – motorised transportation iv. Mobility infrastructure – pedestrians and cyclists
Just Communities	2023	US	Mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Street network
One Planet Living	2025	UK	Equity and local economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Accessibility and inclusion Travel and transport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. Provision of on-site facilities

* In this case, the only analysed open-access document is the Technical manual.

** The document is the Italian version of LEED-Neighbourhood Development (2018, US). The text was translated from the Italian version and could differ from the US original text.

Table 02. A summary of the main topics and indicators emerging from the analysis of the NSA tools.

3.3. Other international documents and frameworks

At the international level, it is possible to identify other documents that do not fall within the scope of NSA tools nor standards. These documents were developed by non-profit bodies to improve the quality of life in urban spaces by prioritising health and well-being in the design of the built environment, are voluntary frameworks and open access.

The Quality of Life (QoL) Framework has been developed by the UK-based charity association QoL Foundation, which carries out independent research into people's well-being in their homes and communities. The Framework is intended to help local communities, professionals, and policymakers in planning, designing, creating, and maintaining good living spaces by addressing six dimensions: (i) a sense of control; (ii) health equity; (iii) connection to nature; (iv) a sense of wonder; (v) mobility; and (vi) connected communities. Each of the dimensions is in turn divided into three specific sub-themes describing their meaning, objectives and impact on health and well-being.

The UN-Habitat document My Neighbourhood can be used as a toolkit in urban design processes to promote sustainability and resilience at the neighbourhood scale. It is an extended "checklist" that integrates design principles across five objectives: (i) compact city; (ii) connected city; (iii) inclusive city; (iv) vibrant city; and (v) resilient city. These objectives span various sectors, including transport, housing, and public spaces, and different design scales, such as neighbourhood, street, open space and building units. Being developed by the same institution, the document also provides indicators for the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) and NUA (New Urban Agenda) targets monitoring, facilitating an inclusive, participatory approach to urban transformation.

Table 03 lists the most relevant indicators of the two documents in line with the research objectives. By comparing the inputs of the two references, it emerges that few topics in the QoL Framework can be transposed in the more comprehensive guidelines objective of this document. The descriptions are generally quite generic and do not provide much detail about specific urban elements. On the other hand, My Neighbourhood represents a significant guide for exploring the concept of physical features that could improve the usability and accessibility of urban open spaces for people with mild disabilities.

Document	Year	Area	Main topics and indicators
Quality of Life Framework 2.0	2024	UK	<p>Connection to nature</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Green and blue spaces <p>Getting around</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ii. Walking, wheeling and cycling iii. Public transport
My Neighbourhood*	2024	World	<p>Proximity and walkability in complete streets Elements that provide comfort of use, safety and security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Pedestrian sidewalks and cycling paths have an appropriate size ii. Sidewalk networks are uninterrupted iii. There are safe crossings iv. There are clear and informative signage and signals, especially for pedestrian orientation v. There are traffic calming measures to lower vehicle speed in pedestrian areas (e.g. pinch-points, medians and refuge islands, speed humps, vegetated buffers) vi. Good street lighting is provided vii. There is a universally accessible pedestrian infrastructure viii. There are places of respite <p>Accessible public transport stops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ix. Shadings structures are provided x. There are comfortable sitting areas xi. Lighting for night-time use is good xii. There are water points <p>Parking areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> xiii. Different car parking areas for different users' needs xiv. Secure bike parking areas are available

* In the table, the topics and indicators merge different objectives and the core design recommendations that accelerate the achievement of the specific vision (named Principle). Meanwhile, the Tips are the design recommendation that supplements specific principles. In the table, these Tips are a bit different from the original document since they summarise “elements” regardless of city objectives.

Table 03. A summary of the main topics and indicators emerging from the analysis of other international documents.

4. PHYSICAL FEATURES TO IMPROVE USABILITY AND ACCESSIBILITY IN URBAN SPACES

By performing a critical analysis of the reported existing tools, documents and protocols, it is possible to identify fifteen recurring “physical elements” that contribute to improving the usability and accessibility of urban spaces. Nevertheless, it should be noted that in many cases the practical modes of implementation of elements are not explicitly detailed, but rather outlined through a general description - or even missing. This mainly concerns the NSA tools, which are mostly designed to promote and assess environmental sustainability in the construction and redevelopment of neighbourhoods. As a consequence, while the ecological dimension is characterised by more precise specifications, the social sustainability side is defined with less obvious connotations. Conversely, national and European standards (specifically the UNI) and other types of voluntary international frameworks (such as UN-Habitat’s My Neighbourhood) clearly identify the main physical features that positively impact on people’s health and well-being, particularly those with mild disabilities.

Table 04 and Table 05 compare and merge the fifteen features identified in the previous review phase. These include urban elements and furniture that people can make use of in pedestrian areas, streets, and open spaces of neighbourhoods, elements not only facilitating and supporting safe movement and mobility, but resting as well. Through the performed critical analysis, two different sections were identified. The first one, summarised in Table 04, refers to six features concerning accessible pedestrian paths and areas, while the second, illustrated in Table 05, focuses on nine urban furniture and services. For each of the relevant features defined based on the review, a brief description is provided, along with a reference to the target users or groups that can benefit the most in space fruition through the features’ implementation. The entries are listed in alphabetical order.

As an exam of the tables reveal, the identified, clustered and defined physical features are not “innovative” in themselves. Rather, their real potential in relation to the objective of improving usability and accessibility of urban spaces lies in their overall organisation and coexistence in the outdoor environment. Some of the elements can be more easily integrated than others, due to the different planning scales they require. This is the case of interventions such as connecting ramps, dividing elements, seats and orientation maps, that require small-scale and punctual operations, opposite to accessible public transport stops, the introduction of water points, and wayfinding systems, which inevitably intersect the urban planning and city services design. A second level of complexity can be identified in the different degree of detail required by the elements, as in some cases their inclusive design should take into account specific aspects of size, materials and ergonomics - whereas for other elements improving liveability in general terms e.g. water points, bicycle parking and vegetation less specifications are needed.

Accessible pedestrian paths and areas		
Inclusive physical features	Target users*	Description and significant characteristics
Connecting ramps	a; b; e	<p>Where there is a difference in level (e.g. one or more steps), a connecting ramp is required to connect surfaces at different heights. These are necessary in particular near pedestrian crossings to ensure safe crossing. They must also be appropriately marked to avoid posing a hazard to people with visual impairments.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Short ramps with a gradient not exceeding 15% are permitted for a maximum height difference of 15 cm (Italian Ministerial Decree 236/1989), with attention to the appropriate design of the side connections.</p>
Dividing elements	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Where there are adjacent paths or areas of different types (e.g. pedestrian, cycle, vehicular), it is recommended to provide separating elements to ensure greater safety (e.g. pinch points, medians and pedestrian refuge islands, vegetated buffers). They can also be used as rest areas, also called slow zones.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> These elements should not obstruct pathways or impede the movement of pedestrians and/or cyclists. In slow zones, the following measures should be considered: a width of 3 m is sufficient for multiple users to have a conversation while walking or resting, while a wheelchair user needs 1.5 m to turn around and 1.8 m to pass other wheelchairs (My Neighbourhood, 2024).</p>
LOGES system	b	<p>Tactile flooring, i.e. the integration of the LOGES system, should be installed near crossings and elements that may constitute obstacles (e.g. near crossings, changes in direction).</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Tactile or contrasting information should be detectable by persons with reduced tactile sensitivity, be made of durable materials and be placed in a logical and sequential manner (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Paving	a; b; d; e	<p>The flooring of paths and pedestrian areas is made of non-slip materials and is uniform and stable. Colours are used that ensure good visual contrast but at the same time do not cause disorientation (e.g. with very strong colours or contrasts) or glare.</p> <p><u>General characteristics</u> It is preferable to use drainage floors to promote floor permeability.</p>

Supporting handrails	a; b; e	<p>In the presence of steep slopes or a large number of steps along the routes, a handrail for support during movement – preferably on both sides of the route – allows for safer and more comfortable movement for people with mobility impairments. The handrail can also serve as an orientation aid for people with visual impairments (e.g. integration of tactile orientation elements).</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> The size and profile of the handrail should make it easy for adults and children to grip. The materials used and the distance from the wall or surface must ensure that it can be used safely without causing injury to users' hands. Handrails should also contrast visually with the surrounding area to make them easily visible and identifiable (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Traffic lights and safe crossing	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Pedestrian crossings controlled by traffic signals provide a safer way to cross the road, particularly in areas with fast-moving vehicles. Crossing signals should be audible, visual and tactile to inform visually impaired pedestrians when it is safe to cross the road.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Traffic signals have to use internationally recognised symbols. They have to be shaded from direct sunlight to ensure adequate visibility and contrast with the background. Depending on the width of the road, sufficient crossing time should be provided to enable people with mobility difficulties to cross safely (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>

* The considered target user groups are: (a) people with motor impairments, (b) people with visual impairments, (c) people with hearing impairments, (d) people with mild cognitive impairments, and (e) elderly people.

Table 04. Inclusive “physical features” to improve usability and accessibility in urban open spaces - Accessible pedestrian paths and areas.

Urban furniture and services

Inclusive physical features	Target users*	Description and significant characteristics
Artificial lighting	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Artificial lighting devices along paths and in urban areas are necessary to guarantee safe use of the space and better orientation even in the evening and at night. They should ensure uniform lighting and avoid direct glare or reflection.</p> <p><u>General characteristics</u> Additional lighting should be provided where necessary to highlight changes in level, potential hazards (e.g. at crossings) and where visual information is provided (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Bicycle parking	e	<p>A sufficient number of bicycle parking spaces is necessary to guarantee a good slow mobility in the neighbourhood and throughout the city.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> The bicycle parking facility is secure, protected from the weather and well-lit (DGNB Districts, 2020). The designated area for bicycle and motorcycle parking must have adequate capacity to prevent bicycles from spilling onto accessible routes. Bicycle parking elements should be easily identifiable through the use of a cane or tactile markings on the ground (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Orientation maps	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Orientation maps, including digital totems and/or tactile maps, provide information and help people find their way around, especially in large urban areas.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Maps and signs are placed at a height that is visible and accessible to people who are sitting, standing or walking. Key information is provided through tactile signs and Braille. In the case of digital totems, glare should be avoided, and an audio information system should be provided as a complement (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Other orientation elements	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Vegetative and/or natural elements (e.g. streams of water, etc.) can aid spatial orientation (colours, smells, noises), as well as improve people's mental and physical well-being, especially for those with mild cognitive disabilities.</p> <p><u>General characteristics</u> Green and/or blue areas help to mitigate the effects of the urban heat island. In presence of vegetative elements, their branches should not obstruct the passageway, and species that may be harmful to</p>

		individuals with allergies should not be selected (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).
Public toilets	a; b; c; d; e	<p>The presence of public toilets in urban areas can be very useful for all city users, especially for the elderly and those with incontinence problems. They must be clearly identified using recognised international symbols and adequately signposted.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> The dimensional specifications are set out in Italian Ministerial Decree 236/1989, while the UNI CEI EN 17210:2021 standard provides suggestions on examples and layouts.</p>
Public transport stops	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Local public transport stops are easy to identify, offer comfortable seating and/or support, provide shelter and are adequately lit at night. It would also be preferable to have local line information systems (e.g. electronic display boards), integrated with acoustic guidance systems in the case of major transport hubs.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Ideally, the maximum walking distance to reach a bus or tram stop should be 200 m as the crow flies. A barrier-free stop has height differences of less than 3 cm to be overcome, as well as marked entry points and movement areas that are not crossed by bicycle paths (DNGB Districts, 2020).</p>
Seats (and respite areas)	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Seats (individual and movable seats, benches, etc.) are appropriately integrated into areas dedicated to rest. Their presence promotes relaxation and socialising when properly positioned in urban spaces. Shading elements, whether natural or artificial, should also be encouraged, so that people can rest even during the hottest and sunniest seasons and days.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> Seats are made from materials that do not overheat, are coloured in contrast to their surroundings so that they can be easily recognised, and are placed in suitable locations to avoid obstructing walkways or pedestrian areas (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Wayfinding	b; c; d; e	<p>Appropriate wayfinding signage (e.g. directional signage, use of clearly legible fonts for text and numbers with good colour contrast) is necessary for better orientation, especially in large open spaces. The information should be complete but concise, localised at decision points of the path or area. It should be provided in alternative formats, such as acoustic, visual or tactile, in accordance with the principle of multisensory perception.</p>

		<p><u>Main characteristics</u> Directional and localisation information agree with ISO 7010:2019 <i>Graphical symbols — Safety colours and safety signs — Registered safety signs</i> (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>
Water points (and other small urban elements)	a; b; c; d; e	<p>Small urban elements such as water points, bollards and/or bins can help people living in the open space, either alone or with pets.</p> <p><u>Main characteristics</u> These elements should be detectable at ground level: it can be achieved by incorporating a consistent profile throughout their height, or by providing some form of ground-level detection, plinth or tactile guide (UNI CEI EN 17210:2021).</p>

* The considered target user groups are: (a) people with motor impairments, (b) people with visual impairments, (c) people with hearing impairments, (d) people with mild cognitive impairments, and (e) elderly people.

Table 05. Inclusive “physical features” to improve usability and accessibility in urban open spaces- Urban furniture and services

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